

European Cloud for Heritage Open Science

Deliverable D4.2

Strategy for Community Building

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Table of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CCI	Cultural and Creative Industries
CH	Cultural heritage
CIDOC CRM	CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage aka Cultural Heritage Cloud
EITF	ECHOES Integration Task Force
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GLAM	Gallery, Library, Archive, Museum
HDTO	Heritage Digital Twin Ontology
H-SeTIS	Heritage – Semantic Tools and Interoperability Survey
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
KOS	Knowledge Organisation Systems
RICHeS	Research Infrastructure for Conservation and Heritage Science
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organisation System
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

Abstract

This deliverable presents the ECHOES strategy for community building in support of the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH). Building on the consultation and mapping activities carried out in D4.1, this strategy document defines the ECCCH community as a federated, practice-based, and non-exclusive ecosystem composed of existing cultural heritage communities, networks, institutions, and emerging communities of practice around shared Cloud tools, services, data, and workflows.

The strategy is organised around four Strategic Areas:

1. activating human-to-human connections through the Cultural Heritage Cloud;
2. establishing a network of trust: towards a federation of Cultural heritage actors;
3. integrating diverse community feedback into the Cultural Heritage Cloud development and operation;
4. towards a common language: sharing languages and concepts through the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

Across these four areas, the deliverable emphasises inclusivity, Open Science, interoperability, capacity-building, participatory feedback, and long-term sustainability.

By linking community building with ECHOES activities in training, integration, governance, assessment, and semantic interoperability, this deliverable provides the strategic basis for the next phase of WP4, which includes the implementation of community building actions, the preparation of the ECCCH Charter, and the future strategy for community growth.

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AI tools were used in the preparation of this document: Grammarly was used to review and improve the English of selected passages. All outputs generated by these tools were reviewed for accuracy and were revised as necessary before inclusion in the document.

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Introduction

What is the “Cloud community”?

Across cultural heritage policy, research, and practice, the concept of community has evolved from a geographically bound or socially homogeneous group toward a more pluralistic, practice-based, and participatory meaning. International frameworks such as those developed by UNESCO and the Council of Europe emphasise the active role of communities in shaping, sustaining, and transmitting cultural heritage, highlighting participation, shared responsibility, and collective agency rather than being related to fixed identities or territories.¹²

In this context, communities are not defined solely by place, legal status, or disciplinary boundaries, but by shared engagement with heritage, whether through professional practice, stewardship, interpretation, the use of data and tools, efforts to preserve and participation in governance and decision-making. This perspective is reflected in the Faro Convention’s definition of a heritage community as people who value specific aspects of cultural heritage and wish, within the framework of public action, to sustain and transmit them to future generations.³

Recent European policy work has highlighted a shift in the understanding of “community” in the cultural heritage sector, moving from passive and loosely defined groupings toward participatory, pluralistic, and agency-driven approaches, in which community involvement is considered an essential component of effective heritage governance.⁴ Work in digital heritage and research infrastructures also stresses the importance of communities of practice, understood as groups of actors who share methods, workflows, responsibilities, and challenges, and who collaborate in order to develop, exchange, and improve practices and knowledge.⁵⁶ Europeana and DARIAH, together with wider European Union guidance such as the Joint Research Centre’s *Communities of Practice Playbook (2021)*, approach communities as voluntary, practice-oriented, and non-exclusive groupings that are formed around shared goals, expertise, and activities rather than formal membership alone.

¹ Council of Europe (2005) *Framework convention on the value of cultural heritage for society (Faro Convention)*.

² UNESCO World Heritage Centre (2007) *Decisions adopted at the 31st session of the World Heritage Committee (WHC-07/31.COM/13B)*.

³ Council of Europe (2005) *Framework convention on the value of cultural heritage for society (Faro Convention)*.

⁴ European Expert Network on Culture (EENC) (2015) *Participatory governance of cultural heritage*.

⁵ DARIAH Community Engagement Working Group (2017) *Community engagement and participation in DARIAH*.

⁶ Europeana Network Association (2021) *Community terms of reference*.

Building on these established approaches and meanings, ECHOES understands a community as a set of cultural heritage actors who share recurring patterns of practice, responsibilities, as well as constraints in their work with cultural heritage data, tools, and services, and who therefore express common needs and expectations toward the Cultural Heritage Cloud. In practical terms, the Cultural Heritage Cloud community is conceived as a federation of existing communities and networks across the cultural heritage landscape, complemented by new communities of practice that emerge around shared Cloud tools, services, and workflows.

In ECHOES, communities are conceived as practice-based and experience-driven groupings and entities, formed around what actors do in relation to cultural heritage and digital infrastructures. Participation in the ECHOES cloud community is voluntary and non-exclusive and does not prevent actors from engaging simultaneously in other institutional, national, or thematic communities, reflecting the hybrid and overlapping roles that characterise the contemporary cultural heritage landscape.

The Cultural Heritage Cloud provides a shared digital landscape that enables access to common resources, data, tools, and services, supports collaboration across institutional and disciplinary boundaries, and fosters the co-development, testing, and refinement of practices and services. In this sense, the Cultural Heritage Cloud functions as an enabling infrastructure that connects communities of practice without replacing existing physical, institutional, or national contexts.

As a cloud community, these actors are connected through their engagement with the Cultural Heritage Cloud digital platform. Communities in ECHOES spread across disciplines, organisational structures, and professional roles. They may also overlap, as actors often operate simultaneously as data producers, users, curators, developers, or mediators within different professional and institutional settings.

This approach avoids treating communities as homogeneous or static entities and instead acknowledges diversity in composition, capacity, and expectations. In line with participatory heritage frameworks, ECHOES treats communities not as passive recipients of services, but as active contributors whose practices, feedback, and agency are essential to the relevance, sustainability, and long-term impact of the Cultural Heritage Cloud.⁷

⁷ Council of Europe (2005) *Framework convention on the value of cultural heritage for society (Faro Convention)*.

This definition provides the reference framework used in the following sections of the strategy. By defining communities through shared practices and engagement, ECHOES supports inclusive participation, iterative co-development of tools and services, and scalable collaboration at European and international levels. The following strategic areas build on this definition by addressing individual agency, institutional and network engagement, integration of community feedback, and the alignment of governance and capacity-building mechanisms with the needs and expectations of ECHOES communities.

Who is Cultural Heritage Cloud for?

Building directly on the evidence gathered in the ECHOES Consultation (deliverable D4.1),⁸ the Cultural Heritage Cloud is intended for a broad range of professional communities that work on, with, or around cultural heritage and thus constitute current or potential users, contributors, intermediaries, or enablers of the Cloud. The consultation carried out in WP4 showed that these communities spread across multiple sectors, disciplines, governance settings, and institutional environments, and that many actors combine responsibilities related to research, study and documentation, protection, conservation, communication and engagement, governance and management, as well as technical development in their daily work.

The Cultural Heritage Cloud is intended in particular for:

- **Cultural heritage professionals**, organisations, SMEs, and institutions, both public and private, including actors working in GLAMs (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums), archaeological sites, built heritage environments, cultural landscapes, and communities' expressions and traditions, as well as other heritage-related fields of practice.
- **Researchers and research-support** actors working with cultural heritage data, methods, processes, infrastructures, and forms of digital scholarship.
- **Digital, data, and technical professionals** involved in the design, development, integration, management, documentation, interoperability, and reuse of digital tools, services, systems, and datasets for or in connection with the cultural heritage domain.
- **Policy, governance, and funding actors**, including public authorities, umbrella organisations, networks, and funders that support coordination, adoption, and the long-term sustainability of the cultural heritage ecosystem.

The ECHOES Consultation also highlighted the importance of engaging with the wider heritage ecosystem, including small and medium-sized organisations, consultancies, non-profit initiatives, and independent or freelance professionals.

⁸ Prandoni, C., et al. (2026) *Report on identification of communities and their needs (D4.1)*.

For this reason, the communities addressed by the Cultural Heritage Cloud are understood in this strategy not as fixed or mutually exclusive user groups, but as interconnected communities of practice whose roles, needs, and modes of engagement with collaborative digital environments may overlap across the cultural heritage landscape.

These categories should be understood as the analytical synthesis of the communities identified through D4.1, as actors for whom the Cultural Heritage Cloud can create value by enabling more structured access to shared data, tools, services, and collaborative digital environments.

Our mission statement

The Cultural Heritage Cloud mission

The Cultural Heritage Cloud provides a shared digital platform for cultural heritage, through which professionals, researchers, and other heritage actors can access and contribute data, scientific resources, training opportunities, and advanced digital tools and services. Built in line with the principles of open access, open science, and interoperability, the Cultural Heritage Cloud supports the co-development, sharing, and reuse of semantically rich digital heritage resources in response to the needs of its communities. In doing so, it enables the emergence of a cultural heritage digital commons: a collaborative, evolving, and reusable environment for generating, connecting, and enriching knowledge on cultural heritage across domains, institutions, and borders.

For more information about the overall Cultural Heritage Cloud mission and vision, please refer to the ECCCH Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda.⁹

The Cultural Heritage Cloud community mission statement

The Cultural Heritage Cloud community brings together the diverse and often fragmented communities engaged in cultural heritage research, stewardship, documentation, conservation, interpretation, and digital innovation around shared Digital Commons. Its mission is to foster a federated, inclusive, and practice-based community in which actors collaborate across disciplines, sectors, and various levels of digital maturity; contribute to the shaping of tools, services, and knowledge; and collectively build more open, interoperable, and sustainable ways of working with cultural heritage. The Cultural Heritage Cloud community connects and strengthens the existing communities through shared experiences, shared infrastructures, shared purposes, and shared responsibility for the future development of the Cloud.

⁹ Demetrescu, E., *et al.* (2026) *ECCCH's Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (D11.1)*.

Towards Common Ground for Community Building

The Cloud strategy for community building relies on the work carried out in several activities within ECHOES, including outreach and collaboration with networks and umbrella organisations. The ECHOES Consultation provided key results and community-facing activities and informed this strategy. This was complemented by desktop research on how the relevant stakeholders' organisations we identified engage with their communities.

Particular focus was also given to the connection of this strategy with other key strategic documents and activities of ECHOES and the wider Cultural Heritage Cloud, including capacity-building, communication and integration strategies, as well as the definition of a participatory governance model.

This transversal approach was particularly relevant for the work on community evaluation and feedback (WP9) and on common technical and natural languages (WP7), where the strategy was designed and tested on specific tools and workflows developed within ECHOES and through the continuous involvement of communities through our member umbrella organisations.

This work led to the adoption of a methodology for writing and discussing the community building strategy across strategic areas.

1.1. Existing strategies from the Cultural Heritage Cloud ecosystem

1.1.1 Lessons learned from umbrella organisations and networks

One of ECHOES' main strengths is its consortium, which connects heritage institutions, universities, and technology partners across Europe and includes 15 networks and umbrella organisations representing over 1,000 cultural institutions and a variety of disciplines.

Relying on ECHOES partners' network expertise is essential for building a strong, inclusive, and sustainable community around the Cultural Heritage Cloud, as they act as multipliers, connectors, and trusted intermediaries across the cultural heritage ecosystem.

In order to better learn from their success stories and their challenges, focus groups and workshops addressing networks in the consortium have been organised during the first 24 months of the project, both to validate and consolidate the results of the consultation survey, enabling also a reflective approach on the analysis carried out in the ECHOES Consultation (D4.1 § 3.4), and to further brainstorm on solutions that the Cloud could offer to facilitate and support the digital practices of their members. Further information about these activities is available in the ECHOES Consultation report.¹⁰

Alongside these networks, ECHOES also operates within a broader ecosystem of ECCCH-related “sister projects”, namely projects funded under parallel European calls that contribute innovative tools and use cases to the Cultural Heritage Cloud. While these projects are distinct from the ECHOES consortium, they represent an important complementary channel for community building, as they bring additional communities, tools, applications, and use cases into relation with the Cloud. In this sense, sister projects function as connected actors within the wider Cultural Heritage Cloud environment, helping to broaden engagement, reinforce alignment across the emerging ecosystem, and support the progressive anchoring of the Cloud in a wider European landscape.

As a complementary effort to the ECHOES Consultation, as well as a preliminary step towards the preparation of the community building strategy, an effort was made to map and reach out to network organisations not represented in the consortium, aspiring to widen the community and “secure” the engagement of these actors, whose contribution is very important in order to anchor the Cloud within the broader European heritage ecosystem.

This activity combined desktop research and reaching out to some partners, aiming to know more about their community or user strategies. The following list of relevant European or international networks and umbrella organisations was compiled with the help of ECHOES partners involved in the community pillar, for a total of more than 30 organisations. This table is available as Annex 1 of this report.

Contacts have already been established with some of these organisations, for instance, during the dissemination of the ECHOES Consultation, or they will be in the near future and throughout the project planning, to continue to grow the community and to broaden engagement with various stakeholders.

¹⁰ Prandoni, C., et al. (2026) *Report on identification of communities and their needs (D4.1)*.

1.1.2 Building on the experience of the private sector

Within the wider organisational landscape of the Cultural Heritage Cloud, private-sector engagement requires specific attention, but it should not be approached as the involvement of a single or homogeneous category of actors. In the cultural heritage ecosystem, private and non-public actors may include technology companies, SMEs, consultancies, private cultural institutions, corporate collections and museums, cultural and creative industries, foundations, associations, cooperatives, and social enterprises. Their relevance to the Cultural Heritage Cloud depends less on legal status alone than on the roles they may play within the Cultural Heritage Cloud ecosystem: being holders of heritage assets, providers of tools and services, developers of applications, mediators of adoption, contributors to training and interoperability, or partners in sustainable service provision.

For this reason, this strategy approaches private-sector engagement through functions and modes of contribution rather than as a fixed stakeholder category. Private and non-public actors may support the Cultural Heritage Cloud as intermediaries that lower barriers in the use of digital tools and services: as multipliers able to extend the reach of the Cultural Heritage Cloud through existing networks and partnerships; as well as integrators that contribute practical knowledge about interoperability, usability, operational constraints, and service sustainability. In this context, their engagement cuts across the strategic areas of this document: supporting user activation and practical adoption in SA1, strengthening networks of trust and cross-sector collaboration in SA2, and contributing to feedback, assessment, and iterative improvement processes in SA3. Further mapping of private and non-public actors will be necessary as the Cultural Heritage Cloud community grows and develops. Such mapping should distinguish between different actor profiles in order to understand their expectations, capacities, and possible contributions to the growth, governance, and long-term sustainability of the Cloud.

1.2. Overview of connected project deliverables and activities

The Cultural Heritage Cloud strategy for community building has been prepared as a direct continuation of the ECHOES Consultation, which aimed at mapping the communities, their digital practices and their needs.

It is a part of a series of strategic documents developed by ECHOES for the Cultural Heritage Cloud. As such, it is linked to several other key documents for the projects. They are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Other project activities related to T4.2

D1.3 Quality and Risk Management Plan	Defines KPIs for community engagement and involvement of stakeholders for building the community	Submitted 31/01/2025 https://zenodo.org/records/17600734
D2.2 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan for months 6-24	Provides a first definition of the main ECCCH stakeholders divided into eight target groups and lists actions to engage them.	Submitted 29/11/2024 https://zenodo.org/records/17513820
D3.1 Integration strategy for datasets, tools and workflows with potential for reuse in ECHOES	The integration strategy is based on a gap analysis which combines the results of the ECHOES consultation and the inventory of existing datasets, tools and workflows, informed by the communities' needs.	Submitted https://zenodo.org/records/17751335
D3.2 Integration roadmap	Refers to Collaborative Research Scenarios (CRS) as bridge between the planned infrastructure's technical aspects and its community dimensions. CRS are collaborative, interactive moments with communities' representatives to co-design the Cloud, understanding what is needed for them to benefit from the Digital Continuum and documenting the impact of ECHOES services.	Submitted 10/12/2025 https://zenodo.org/records/17751670
D5.1 Principles for Capacity-building and Training	Acknowledges capacity-building focused on people (Principle 1) as a tool to promote community engagement.	Submitted 29/11/2025 https://zenodo.org/records/17513834
D5.3 Strategy and Roadmap for Capacity-building, Training and Knowledge Transfer	Aligns with the community building principles in proposing learning resources that focus on people, are co-curated and adaptable to different knowledge systems and language communities.	Submitted 11/12/2025 https://zenodo.org/records/17747265
D10.1 Founding Principles of the Cloud Governance	Reports on the collaborative process through which the governance requirements were formulated and to the principles for building a sustainable community	Submitted 30/05/2025 https://zenodo.org/records/17599162
D10.2 Governance model of the legal entity	Reports on the research and ECHOES' proposition for the legal entity that will support the future Cloud. The governance design will include the representation of the CH communities.	Submitted 29/05/2026
D11.1 ECCCH's Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda	Section dedicated to communities.	Submitted 29/05/2026

1.3. Methodological approach to community building

The methodological approach adopted in WP4 for community building is grounded in the findings of Deliverable D4.1, which brought together consultation and mapping activities to identify the needs, barriers, expectations, and patterns of engagement across the cultural heritage ecosystem. Building on this evidence, and on the broader analysis of the sector, the present strategy recognises that the Cultural Heritage Cloud must evolve as a federation of existing communities, practices, and networks, complemented by new communities of practice emerging around shared digital tools, services, data, and collaborative workflows.

In this context, community building is understood as a progressive and multi-layered process involving individuals, organisations, technological infrastructures, and shared conceptual frameworks. The strategy, therefore, adopts an open and enabling model through which different actors across the cultural heritage landscape can engage with the Cultural Heritage Cloud according to their needs, roles, capacities, and levels of digital maturity. At the same time, this approach recognises that the specific value of the Cloud lies in connecting people and institutions, as well as providing a shared digital environment through which collaboration can be organised, supported, scaled, and sustained through common access to data, tools, services, workflows, and semantic resources.

Open Science principles are embedded in this methodological approach as a condition for sustainable community building. The strategy supports open access, interoperability, reuse, and shared governance by ensuring that community-facing outputs developed within ECHOES, including guidance materials, consultation results where appropriate, training resources, glossaries, vocabularies, and semantic artefacts, are documented and made accessible through suitable project and Cloud infrastructures. Where possible, these outputs should be accompanied by clear licensing conditions, stable references, versioning information, provenance records, and documented responsibilities for maintenance and update. This is particularly important for resources intended to support reuse across communities, such as multilingual glossaries, semantic artefacts, metadata guidance, and other shared conceptual resources. In this way, Open Science is treated as a practical framework for enabling transparency, long-term access, community contribution, and the reuse of knowledge, data, and tools within the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

The consultation results presented in D4.1 highlighted several key dimensions that are deemed necessary to build a sustainable and inclusive community ecosystem around the Cloud. These dimensions informed the identification of the strategic areas that provide the structural pillars of the present strategy.

In this document, “**Strategic Areas**” are understood as strategic directions of action through which the community building strategy can be implemented, tested, and refined across the development of the Cultural Heritage Cloud. Each Strategic Area addresses a particular dimension of participation and collaboration while also clarifying how the Cloud can support that dimension in practice.

More specifically, the analysis on the existing communities in the cultural heritage sector pointed to the need to support individuals to participate in collaborative knowledge creation and valorise their contributions; to rely on existing professional networks and organisations as trusted gateways to broader communities; to establish mechanisms through which communities can express needs and provide feedback on the development of tools, services, and workflows; and to ensure that collaboration across disciplines, sectors, and language communities is supported by shared concepts and multilingual communication. Within ECHOES, they also define the main ways in which the Cultural Heritage Cloud can generate value, by enabling access to shared resources, supporting interaction across institutional and disciplinary boundaries, facilitating feedback and co-development, and creating a more interoperable and inclusive environment for cultural heritage practice.

On this basis, the strategy is structured around four complementary strategic areas, each addressing a specific dimension of community building within the Cultural Heritage Cloud:

- 1 Strengthening individual agency and enabling human-to-human collaboration.**
- 2 Mobilising existing networks and organisations as entry points to broader communities.**
- 3 Establishing tools and workflows that support community contributions and feedback.**
- 4 Fostering a shared conceptual and multilingual framework for cross-domain collaboration.**

These strategic areas should be understood as mutually reinforcing elements of a single community building framework. Together, they provide the methodological foundation for guiding community engagement activities within ECHOES and for supporting the long-term development of the Cultural Heritage Cloud community. In this sense, they form the bridge between the evidence gathered in community analyses and the subsequent implementation, governance, and community growth activities that will shape the next phase of the project.

Strategic Area 1: Activating human-to-human connections through the Cultural Heritage Cloud

Objective:

The first Strategic Area emphasises empowering individuals to actively engage in collaborative knowledge creation. This requires understanding of the value of collaboration as well as acquiring the necessary skills and conceptual frameworks and learning to effectively use the Cultural Heritage Cloud's tools for sharing and co-constructing knowledge.

Key emphasis:

- Capacity-building and empowerment at the individual level
- Understanding collaboration as a practice and value
- Ability to use tools, concepts, and shared infrastructures
- Considered a precondition for the effective implementation of all other strategic areas

SA1 is therefore composed of:

- **SA1.1 Demonstrating the value of collaboration**
- **SA1.2 Capacity-building and mutual learning**
- **SA1.3 Enabling individual agency, promoting collective intelligence**

Collaboration lies at the core of the Cultural Heritage Cloud's mission. While shared tools and workflows are important enablers of collaborations, their success relies on key social and institutional factors. While the literature¹¹ highlights different factors based on types of collaboration and stakeholders (collaborative research, collaborative learning, university-industry collaboration, etc.), all agree on the importance of relationship factors, including one-to-one relationships between actors, trust, and stakeholder engagement.

As a sociotechnical system, the Cultural Heritage Cloud recognises that human components of collaboration are essential to delivering its services to their full value. Strategic Area 1 for community building focuses on the social components of collaboration, as the founding act of the Cultural Heritage Cloud community of practices and experiences. It relies on three main ideas:

- Collaboration benefits all types of stakeholders involved in digital cultural heritage and contributes to an interdisciplinary community.
- Capacity-building, mutual learning, and positive interdependence increase the effectiveness of collaboration and strengthen communities.
- Individual agency is an asset to collaboration, increases collective intelligence, and contributes to an open and motivated community.

SA1.1 Demonstrating the value of collaboration

Like many other fields, digital cultural heritage is largely structured around incentive structures that reward competition over collaboration. This can be exemplified by the increased importance of project or grant-based funding, cultural heritage institutions competing on digital presence and innovation, audience and visitor engagement, etc. This is perhaps even more observable in the academic field related to digital cultural heritage, where increased scarcity of funding often leads to siloed or lost knowledge, short-term focus, structural inequities, or redundancies.

While there is a place for competition within controlled collaborative frameworks, Cultural Heritage Cloud communities are based on the belief that collaboration is the best way to achieve the different stakeholders' objectives. This affirmation is supported by the literature on the different functions and objectives that the Cultural Heritage Cloud offers.

¹¹ Johnson, D.W., & Johnson, R.T. (1989) *Cooperation and Competition Theory and Research*.

First, collaborative learning can increase capacity-building learning outputs¹² by enhancing critical thinking and fostering mutual learning. This non-hierarchical participation approach is the core of the cloud community vision and its capacity-building strategy. Active idea exchanges, peer explanation, and accountability are key mechanisms to reach the full benefit of collaboration in terms of increased critical thinking and problem solving.¹³

Cooperation outperforms competitive or individualistic efforts for producing new knowledge and outcomes, for reinforcing interpersonal bonds, and for increasing the overall psychological health of the people involved.¹⁴ However, the experience of the field of education shows collaboration is often more rhetoric than reality and needs both strong leadership and systemic changes to be correctly implemented.¹⁵

Based on the community feedback from the ECHOES Consultation and the collective experience of its partners, ECHOES firmly believes these affirmations hold true for collaboration in the field of cultural heritage, including in the creation, reuse and dissemination of new knowledge, and the conservation and valorisation of cultural heritage.

The Cultural Heritage Cloud, through its collaborative environment and community building approach, aims at increasing social interdependence between the individual members of its community by making sure that collaborative actions and mutual support are not only facilitated but also rewarded.

SA1.2 Capacity-building and mutual learning

Capacity-building is a precondition for meaningful participation in the Cultural Heritage Cloud. Access to shared tools, services, and data is not sufficient if potential participants do not have the skills, confidence, conceptual orientation, or institutional support needed to use them effectively. For this reason, capacity-building within SA1 should be understood not only as technical training, but as a reciprocal process of mutual learning through which cultural heritage actors learn from one another while contributing their own expertise, practices, and situated knowledge to the Cultural Heritage Cloud community.

¹² Annett, N. (1997) *Collaborative learning: definitions, benefits, applications and dangers in the writing center*.

¹³ Gokhale, A.A. (1995) 'Collaborative learning enhances critical thinking'.

¹⁴ Johnson, D.W., *et al.* (1989) *Cooperation and Competition Theory and Research*.

¹⁵ Jenni, R.W., *et al.* (2004) 'Cooperation and collaboration: Reality or rhetoric?'

This approach is closely connected to the concept of positive interdependence in collaborative learning. In cooperative settings, collaboration becomes effective when participants understand that their own success is linked to the contribution and success of others, while still remaining individually accountable for their own role.^{16 17} Applied to the Cloud, this means that capacity-building should not position some actors simply as trainers and others as passive recipients of knowledge. Rather, it should create conditions in which cultural heritage professionals, researchers, technical developers, infrastructure providers, educators, and community mediators can exchange knowledge across different fields of expertise and levels of digital maturity.

Mutual learning is particularly important for the Cultural Heritage Cloud because the knowledge required for effective collaboration is distributed across different communities. Heritage professionals may bring domain expertise, curatorial knowledge, conservation experience, and understanding of institutional constraints. Technical actors may contribute knowledge of data modelling, interoperability, digital tools, and infrastructure development. Researchers, educators, and networks can contribute methodological frameworks, training practices, and channels for wider dissemination. The Cultural Heritage Cloud community will only become effective and impactful if these different forms of expertise are placed in dialogue and translated into shared practices. In practical terms, this requires training resources, onboarding activities, workshops, peer-learning formats, guidance materials, reusable examples, and spaces for exchange that are adaptable to different levels of digital maturity. It also requires explicit alignment with WP5, where capacity-building and training are developed as community-oriented instruments for addressing fragmentation, technical knowledge gaps, barriers to communication, and uneven access to digital expertise. Within the community building strategy, these activities should therefore be understood not only as mechanisms for skills development, but also as tools for strengthening mutual learning and positive interdependence across the Cultural Heritage Cloud community.

Consequently, capacity-building consequently has a social as well as a technical function. It helps participants understand not only how to use tools, but also how their own knowledge and practices can contribute to shared workflows, common resources, and the wider development of the Cloud. In this sense, mutual learning supports trust, reduces barriers to efficient and meaningful participation, and enables different actors to recognise their role within a collaborative infrastructure.

¹⁶ Johnson, D.W., & Johnson, R.T. (1989) *Cooperation and Competition Theory and Research*.

¹⁷ Scager, K., *et al.* (2016) 'Collaborative learning in higher education: evoking positive interdependence'.

SA1.3 Enabling individual agency, promoting collective intelligence

Individual agency is essential to the development of the Cultural Heritage Cloud community, but it should not be understood as individual action detached from collective work. In communities of practice, individuals participate through shared activities, mutual engagement, and the gradual development of common resources, vocabularies, routines, and forms of expertise (Wenger, 1998).¹⁸ From this perspective, agency means that individual actors are able to identify a meaningful role for themselves within the Cloud, whether as users, contributors, testers, curators, trainers, developers, mediators, or adopters of shared practices.

Therefore, supporting agency, requires more than opening access to a digital platform. It requires clear contribution pathways, low barriers to participation, recognition of different forms of expertise, and opportunities for individuals to see how their input can influence the development of tools, services, workflows, and shared knowledge. This is particularly important in a heterogeneous field such as cultural heritage, where relevant expertise is distributed across institutions, professions, disciplines, and levels of digital maturity.

At the same time, individual agency becomes strategically valuable when it contributes to collective intelligence. Research on collective intelligence shows that group performance is not determined only by the expertise of individual members, but also by the quality of interaction, balanced participation, and the ability of groups to integrate distributed knowledge (Woolley et al., 2010).¹⁹ This means that the Cultural Heritage Cloud should create the conditions through which individual contributions become visible, reusable, and connected to common objectives.

Within ECHOES, this understanding of agency is supported by the wider capacity-building and training activities developed in connection with WP5, as well as by community-facing mechanisms such as onboarding resources, workshops, guidance materials, feedback channels, and opportunities to participate in testing and co-design. These mechanisms help individuals move from passive use toward more active forms of contribution, while also supporting the positive interdependence needed for collaborative work across the Cultural Heritage Cloud community.

¹⁸ Wenger, E. (1998), *Communities of practice: Learning, meaning and identity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

¹⁹ Woolley, A. W., Chabris, C. F., Pentland, A., Hashmi, N., & Malone, T. W. (2010). Evidence for a collective intelligence factor in the performance of human groups. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 330(6004), 686–688. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1193147>

Digital environments can support this process by enabling asynchronous collaboration, shared documentation, discussion spaces, issue-tracking, feedback mechanisms, versioned resources, and co-design activities. However, technology alone does not produce collective intelligence. It must be accompanied by trust, mediation, shared norms, and recognition of contributions. Within SA1, the objective is therefore to ensure that individuals are not passive users of the Cultural Heritage Cloud, but active participants whose expertise, feedback, and situated knowledge contribute to the collective development of the Cloud community.

Rationale for private sector engagement

Within this Strategic Area, private actors from the Cultural and Creative Industries sector participate as users, while ICT businesses contribute as **enablers of adoption and engagement**. By participating as early adopters and service providers, they facilitate access to digital tools and services, supporting users in understanding and experimenting with the capabilities of the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

Through practical use cases, training activities, and direct interaction with end users, private ICT actors help lower barriers to entry and foster confidence in the use of digital solutions. In doing so, they support the activation of individuals and communities, enabling meaningful knowledge exchange and collaboration across domains.

Concrete participation opportunities for companies include:

- Joining as users of Cloud tools and services, accessing data, dashboards, and platforms, and participating in collaborative projects.
- Joining as developers, creating applications, services, or technical extensions that enhance Cloud functionality.

Strategic Area 2: Establishing a network of trust: towards a federation of cultural heritage actors

Objective:

The second Strategic Area highlights the importance of building the Cultural Heritage Cloud community by leveraging existing networks, organisations and associations – whether public, non-profit or private – rather than creating parallel structures. In turn, this approach will strengthen governance, resilience and inclusivity.

Key emphasis:

- Acting at the organisational and institutional level
- Using existing communities as entry points
- Supporting European and non-European collaboration through networks

SA2 is therefore composed of:

- **SA2.1 Grounding the Cultural Heritage Cloud in existing community organisations and institutions**
- **SA2.2 Enabling and mediating dialogue between various types of stakeholders**
- **SA2.3 Fostering interinstitutional and transnational collaboration**

Strategic Area 2 addresses the organisational, interinstitutional and cross-sectoral dimensions of community building within the Cloud. As the consultation presented in WP4 has shown, participation in the cultural heritage ecosystem is already structured through a wide range of organisations, umbrella bodies, professional networks, institutional partnerships, and sectoral intermediaries that shape trust, legitimacy, visibility, and access to opportunities. Cultural heritage actors often engage with new initiatives through the professional and institutional environments in which they already operate.

For this reason, ECHOES approaches community building as the progressive anchoring of the Cloud within existing ecosystems of collaboration. In this federative perspective, the Cultural Heritage Cloud is strengthened when it works through, with, and across already established communities, organisations, and institutions. This includes not only the networks represented in the consortium, but also partners, sister projects and cascading grants beneficiaries that contribute complementary tools, applications, use cases, and communities to the wider Cloud environment.

Existing networks, organisations, and connected projects are therefore understood as trusted entry points for participation and collaboration. They provide channels through which the Cloud can reach broader communities credibly and sustainably, while also helping to extend engagement across institutional, disciplinary, and national boundaries. At the same time, the specific value of the Cloud lies in providing a shared digital environment through which these actors can connect more systematically, contribute and access resources, and participate in common workflows and forms of collaboration.

SA2.1 Grounding the Cultural Heritage Cloud through existing community organisations and institutions

ECHOES understands the Cloud as a federation of existing communities, practices, and networks. In parallel with this, SA2.1 develops this principle at the organisational level. It builds on the premise that the Cloud has broad and lasting engagement when it is anchored in institutions, umbrella bodies, and community organisations that already organise participation, represent constituencies, coordinate exchange, and support trust-building across the cultural heritage ecosystem.

While existing organisations and networks serve as channels for communication or dissemination, they are also active environments of collaboration, representation, and professional exchange, and they often provide the conditions through which communities assess the relevance and credibility of new initiatives.

Building such structures allows the Cloud to connect with communities in ways that are more legible, more trusted, and more scalable than approaches based only on direct outreach to isolated actors.

This perspective also has important implications for the future development of the Cloud. At this stage, the strategy does recognise that community building in the Cloud has a clear organisational dimension, and that existing institutions and networks will be essential for shaping how participation, representation, and longer-term integration may evolve.

Lessons learned from: case studies

The development of the Cultural Heritage Cloud within the ECHOES project requires a sustainable and inclusive community structure capable of supporting collaboration across the diverse cultural heritage ecosystem. This includes GLAMs, research infrastructures, digital humanities communities, capacity-building institution and ICT providers.

Two mature European initiatives provide valuable reference models for such a community structure: the Europeana Network Association (ENA) and the Archives Portal Europe Foundation (APEF). Both organisations support large European cultural heritage infrastructures and have developed governance models that combine community participation, strategic coordination, and operational management.

While the two initiatives differ in scope and organisational design, they offer complementary lessons that can inform the development of the Cloud community.

Community Structures and Governance Models

Europeana Network Association (ENA)

ENA functions as the community pillar of the Europeana Initiative, supporting collaboration and knowledge exchange across the cultural heritage sector. The association has approximately 6,000 individual members and operates through a bottom-up participation model.

Its governance structure includes:

- Management Board, responsible for strategic leadership and representation
- Members Council, which defines priorities and steers activities
- Thematic Communities, where members collaborate around specific areas of interest
- Working Groups and Task Forces, addressing ongoing and time-limited topics

ENA communities function as collaborative spaces where professionals from heritage institutions, research organisations, and the ICT sectors can exchange knowledge, develop best practices, and contribute to Europeana’s strategy.

The structure emphasises openness, flexibility, and community initiative. Participation is voluntary and largely self-organised within thematic communities.

Archives Portal Europe Foundation (APEF)

APEF manages and develops Archives Portal Europe, which aggregates archival descriptions from institutions across Europe and provides open access to archival heritage.

Unlike ENA’s individual membership model, APEF is structured as a foundation with institutional governance. Its core governance bodies include:

- Assembly of Associates, composed of institutional members that define strategy and approve budgets
- Governing Board, responsible for managing the foundation and implementing strategy
- APEF Bureau, the operational staff responsible for daily activities

Beyond formal governance, the APEF ecosystem includes several distributed community roles:

- Country Managers, national-level coordinators connecting the portal with archival communities in their countries
- Content Providers, institutions contributing archival metadata and collections
- Institution Managers, responsible for technical coordination of data ingestion
- Ambassadors, volunteers supporting outreach and engagement activities

This structure supports a network of more than 1,300 contributing institutions across Europe and beyond.

Similarities Between the Models

Despite differences in governance and scope, ENA and APEF share several structural characteristics that are highly relevant for the design of the Cloud community.

1. Multi-level community ecosystems

Both organisations combine multiple layers of participation and governance, demonstrating the importance of multi-level governance structures that balance strategic leadership with distributed participation.

2. *Broad stakeholder engagement*

Both models rely on the participation of diverse actors across the cultural heritage ecosystem. Such diversity of stakeholders is essential for the Cloud vision, which aims to support collaboration across disciplines and institutional types.

3. *Knowledge sharing and open collaboration*

Both initiatives emphasise open knowledge exchange and collaboration through digital tools and community activities, mechanisms which support the development of shared standards, best practices, and innovative digital services.

4. *Alignment with European policy values*

ENA and APEF both operate within the broader framework of European policy priorities, including open access to cultural heritage, FAIR data principles, inclusiveness and diversity, accessibility and multilingualism. These values are equally central to the mission of the Cloud.

Key Differences Between the Models

While both initiatives offer relevant examples, they also highlight different approaches to community organisation.

1. *Individual vs institutional membership*

One major difference concerns membership structures. ENA operates with individual membership, encouraging broad participation and grassroots engagement across professional communities. APEF, by contrast, relies on institutional membership through its Assembly of Associates, which contributes financially and shapes strategic decisions. For the Cloud, a hybrid model combining institutional participation with individual community engagement may provide the most effective balance between sustainability and inclusiveness.

2. *Domain-specific vs cross-domain scope*

APEF focuses specifically on the archival sector, while ENA covers the broader cultural heritage domain but remains closely tied to the Europeana ecosystem. The Cloud aims to support a cross-domain infrastructure. This broader scope implies greater complexity in governance, coordination, and standards development.

3. *Community autonomy vs operational coordination*

ENA communities operate with a high degree of autonomy, enabling bottom-up collaboration but sometimes leading to fragmentation between thematic groups. APEF, in contrast, maintains stronger central coordination through its governance bodies and national Country Manager network. The Cloud will likely need to balance community autonomy with mechanisms ensuring coordination and strategic alignment.

Challenges Identified in the Models

Both initiatives highlight challenges that are highly relevant for the Cloud community.

➤ *Risk of siloed communities*

Autonomous communities can develop separate agendas and limited interaction across thematic areas.

➤ *Dependence on institutional capacity*

Infrastructure growth depends on the ability of institutions to digitise collections and produce high-quality metadata.

➤ *Continuity of participation*

Changes in institutional staff or responsibilities can disrupt coordination roles such as national representatives or data managers.

➤ *Diversity of standards and practices*

Differences in national and institutional standards require flexible but interoperable approaches to metadata and data management. These challenges highlight the need for governance models that support coordination, sustainability, and knowledge exchange across a highly heterogeneous community.

Emerging Recommendations for the Cultural Heritage Cloud

Drawing on the experiences of ENA and APEF, several recommendations emerge for shaping the Cloud community.

1. *Develop a multi-level governance structure*

The Cultural Heritage Cloud should combine:

- strategic governance bodies
- operational coordination teams
- thematic communities
- national or regional coordination networks

Such a layered structure can support both strategic direction and grassroots participation.

2. *Introduce national or regional coordination roles*

Following the APEF Country Manager model, the Cloud could establish national liaison roles responsible for connecting local communities with the European infrastructure and facilitating engagement and data contribution.

3. *Foster cross-community collaboration*

Mechanisms should be developed to prevent siloed activity, such as:

- joint working groups across thematic communities
- liaison roles connecting different domains
- collaborative task forces addressing interdisciplinary topics

4. *Support Community Participation and Capacity-building*

Low-barrier participation opportunities should be created for a wide range of actors, including:

- institutions
- individual experts
- researchers
- volunteers and user communities

Training, networking events, and collaborative projects can strengthen community engagement.

5. *Promote Shared and Flexible Standards*

The Cloud should support the development of shared application profiles and interoperable standards while allowing for diversity in national and institutional practices.

In conclusion, the governance models developed by ENA and APEF demonstrate how large European cultural heritage communities can successfully support digital infrastructures through distributed collaboration, shared standards, and open participation.

For the Cloud, the key challenge will be to combine the bottom-up community dynamics exemplified by ENA with the structured coordination mechanisms developed by APEF. By integrating these approaches, the Cloud can build a sustainable and inclusive community capable of supporting Europe's evolving (digital) cultural heritage ecosystem.

SA2.2 Enabling and mediating dialogue between various types of stakeholders

SA2.2 addresses a distinct challenge, enabling meaningful dialogue between the different types of stakeholders that make up the broader cultural heritage ecosystem. As already mentioned, the communities addressed by the Cloud do not form a homogeneous group. They differ in mission, scale, professional language, institutional culture, digital maturity, and expectations toward data, tools, services, and collaboration. Cultural heritage institutions, research organisations, infrastructure providers, technical developers, public authorities, networks, and other actors often approach the Cloud from different positions and with different priorities. For this reason, community building cannot rely only on visibility or access. It also requires forms of mediation that make exchange, mutual understanding, and cooperation possible across these differences.

In the context of the Cloud, dialogue should therefore be understood not as a purely communicative activity, but as a strategic condition for participation in a shared digital environment. The Cloud can only function as a collaborative infrastructure if the needs, constraints, and capacities of different stakeholder groups are made legible to one another and progressively translated into shared objectives, common practices, and workable forms of cooperation. This requires spaces, mechanisms, and intermediary structures through which communities can encounter one another, express priorities, identify barriers, and contribute to the shaping of the Cloud in ways that are both meaningful and realistic.

The specific value of the Cloud in this respect lies in its capacity to support more continuous and structured forms of interaction than those usually enabled by isolated consultations or one-off events. By providing a shared digital environment, the Cloud can help transform dispersed stakeholder relations into more sustained forms of collaboration around common resources, workflows, tools, and services. At the same time, such collaboration does not emerge automatically from infrastructure alone.

It depends on trusted channels of mediation, on opportunities for feedback and exchange, and on mechanisms capable of connecting communities.

This mediating function is especially important in an ecosystem such as the Cloud, where ECHOES operates alongside a wider set of connected actors and initiatives. In addition to the organisations represented in the consortium, the broader Cloud environment includes sister projects and cascading grants beneficiaries that contribute complementary applications, services, datasets, and use cases, while also bringing their own communities and collaboration networks into relation with the emerging Cloud ecosystem.

In this sense, dialogue within the Cloud is not limited to established institutional stakeholders alone, but also extends across projects, funded initiatives, and different layers of participation in the wider European heritage landscape. Sister projects therefore matter to the strategic area as representatives of specific user communities, as well as important mediating actors that broaden the reach of the Cloud, diversify the communities connected to it, and help reinforce alignment across the developing ecosystem.

On this basis, the following section is concerned with the practical and strategic mechanisms through which such dialogue can be enabled. These mechanisms may take different forms, including consultations, workshops, cross-sector exchanges, ambassador-type approaches, coordinated feedback channels, and funded activities that activate communities and support their engagement with the Cloud. Among these, the Cascading Grants Programme is particularly important because it creates a structured way to extend participation beyond the consortium, involve new communities, and support more distributed and community-grounded forms of interaction with the Cloud.

Lessons learned from: the ECHOES Cascading Grants Programme

The [ECHOES Cascading Grants Programme](#) provides small grants to third-party cultural heritage actors to help build and expand the community around the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage.

The programme funds up to 50 projects across three calls, with grants between €30.000 and €60.000 per project to organisations contributing to the Cultural Heritage Cloud ecosystem. The programme is structured across three calls: Call 1, focused on contributing datasets for use in the Cultural Heritage Cloud, was launched in 2025 through a two-stage application process, with proposal deadlines in May and October 2025 and funded projects publicly announced in 2026; Call 2, focused on engagement, collaboration, communication, dissemination, and capacity-building, was launched in

2025 through a one-stage process, with a proposal deadline in January 2026; Call 3, focused on datasets and vertical applications, is expected to be published in January 2027.

While the first²⁰ and third calls²¹ fund organisations or consortia to contribute datasets or applications for use in the Cloud, the second call²² on Community Engagement and Collaboration more directly targets the development of the Cloud community, by encouraging cultural heritage institutions - particularly small and medium-sized ones - to join it.

The objective is to activate new community members, providing them with the skills necessary to use and contribute to the Cloud, involve a wide range of cultural heritage domains, and increase geographical balance across EU Member States.

The call is addressed not only to cultural heritage institutions, but also to networks and umbrella organisations, in order to maximise impact. Indeed, involving networks as grant beneficiaries and important players supporting the Cloud can make cultural heritage institutions more likely to explore and adopt it, with networks providing benefits in terms of trust and legitimacy, the Cloud endorsement and peer validation.

Activities funded by the second call include surveys and sector consultations; communication, dissemination and awareness raising events about the Cloud; the organisation of capacity-building and training events, including workshops, webinars, online courses, the production of guidelines or toolkits and the setting up of ambassadors schemes across Europe.

At the time of writing, 20 projects have been selected which represent cultural heritage domains spanning from libraries, archives and museums to religious and fashion heritage, from audiovisual and media to architecture and landscape. The successful proposals engage new actors and achieve a geographical representation which is complementary to that of ECHOES. It can be said that each funded project strengthens connections across disciplines and countries and can therefore become a multiplier, promoting the Cloud within its national and regional context.

During the implementation phase, successful projects will be mentored by ECHOES partners and interact with ECHOES Work Packages, in particular, with WP2, WP4 and WP5 in order to align with and contribute to efforts in the three different areas: communication and dissemination, community building and training and capacity-building.

²⁰ Published in February 2025. Awarded projects list available on the ECHOES website: <https://www.echoes-CULTURAL HERITAGE CLOUD.eu/first-call-awards/>.

²¹ Opening in January 2027. See ECHOES website: <https://www.echoes-CULTURAL HERITAGE CLOUD.eu/cascading-grants/>.

²² Published in September 2025. See project website for more details. <https://www.echoes-ecch.eu/second-call/>

In addition, funded projects will be integral to the evaluation and improvement of the entire Cloud digital ecosystem and will be asked to give feedback on the functioning of the Cloud, as it will be developing in the course of time.

Across the three calls and beyond the monetary value, by bringing new institutions into the Cloud ecosystem, the ECHOES cascading grants are designed not only to promote the creation and sharing of datasets or applications but, through capacity-building and community engagement activities, they aim to expand the Cloud stakeholders base and user community, fostering in participants a stronger commitment to and a sense of ownership in the Cloud which is meant to last beyond the funding period and contribute to its sustainability.

Ambassador-type approaches can reinforce these community building activities by extending the reach of the Cultural Heritage Cloud through trusted individuals already embedded in national, thematic, or professional environments. In strategic terms, such actors can help raise awareness of the Cloud opportunities, encourage participation in training and engagement activities, support onboarding, and mediate between existing communities and the Cloud by communicating needs, barriers, and opportunities back to the project. In this way, ambassador schemes can strengthen trust and support a more distributed and community-grounded model of engagement.

These forms of mediation and community activation also intersect closely with the challenges addressed in Strategic Area 4. Within the Cloud, dialogue between stakeholder groups depends on a set of factors, including creating opportunities for participation or ensuring that communities can engage across linguistic, disciplinary, and institutional differences. In this sense, the Cloud must support trusted channels of interaction, together with accessible communication, multilingual engagement, and the progressive development of shared concepts that allow diverse communities to work with common resources, tools, and services.

SA2.3 Fostering interinstitutional and transnational collaboration

Networks – professional and institutional – and umbrella organisations are not only entry points into the community but active participants in how ECHOES is run. They are strongly represented in the project's core activities, and this participation will be extended to future Cloud governance. In the project, they offer access to and engagement with a very wide range of cultural heritage communities, thus contributing to raising awareness about the project and its collaboration opportunities to the cultural heritage actors they represent. They also actively encourage and support participation of their – often – transnational and transdisciplinary networks in the project's activities and funding opportunities.

The ECHOES work package working on governance is developing a proposal that would include participatory mechanisms for communities and networks, and their representation in the Community Advisory Board.²³ The latter would offer guidance and advice to the executive body of the Cloud to ensure that communities are heard properly while also efficiently disseminating information to the networks and encouraging cross-community and transnational dialogue and cooperation within the Cloud.

Furthermore, the Cultural Heritage Cloud ecosystem actively fosters interinstitutional and transnational collaboration. Beyond this extensive ramification across Europe, the Cultural Heritage Cloud and their respective cascading grants projects contribute directly to the platform through new tools, use cases, capacity-building resources, and cascading grants that serve as gateways to what the Cloud has to offer.

Each sister project tailors its services to the needs of specific communities, enabling those communities to engage with and participate in the Cloud network. The TEXTaiLES project exemplifies this approach, connecting textile professionals and researchers with emerging technologies to support the full digitisation lifecycle of textile objects.

Furthermore, many Cultural Heritage projects feature their own cascading grant programmes, financing dozens of smaller initiatives in diverse subjects. In 2026, eight additional projects will join this network, further broadening its reach and impact.

Finally, workshops and joint activities play a concrete role in reinforcing working relationships and collaborations. These events serve a dual purpose. First, they offer spaces for experience and knowledge exchange, and for community feedback gathering for the project. Second, they help foster interpersonal and interinstitutional relationships that underpin durable collaboration.

²³ Petitcol, R., *et al.* (2026) *Governance Model of the legal entity (D10.2)*.

Rationale for private sector engagement

Within the network-of-trust framework, private CCIs and ICT businesses contribute as **multipliers and connectors**, extending the reach of the Cultural Heritage Cloud ecosystem through their networks and partnerships. Their involvement facilitates cross-sector collaboration and supports the integration of diverse stakeholders, including cultural institutions, research organisations, and technology providers.

By acting as intermediaries between technological solutions and user needs, private actors support organisations in adopting Cloud services and contribute to building trust in the Cloud. Their operational experience and engagement in real-world contexts further strengthen the reliability and relevance of the ecosystem.

Concrete participation opportunities for companies include:

- Supporting their network institutions in migrating, curating, and managing digital assets within the Cloud.
- Offering value-added services such as data preparation, metadata enrichment, interoperability, and training; in short companies help institutions make their digital assets ready, usable, and compatible, while also training staff to use them efficiently.
- Strengthening openness, reducing vendor lock-in, and creating long-term value for both clients and service providers.

Strategic Area 3: Integrating diverse community feedback into the Cultural Heritage Cloud development and operation

Objective:

The third Strategic Area seeks to ensure that digital tools and workflows serve as enabling infrastructures for collaboration by continuously capturing user needs, expectations and feedback, and aligning technical development with community practices.

Key emphasis:

- Expression of needs before, during and after use
- Ongoing feedback loops rather than one-off consultation
- Sustainability through continuous user tool alignment
- Capacity-building to allow users and communities to understand, use and collaboratively improve tools

SA3 is therefore composed of:

- **SA3.1 An active and continuous identification of needs**
- **SA3.2 Community-backed objectives and priorities**
- **SA3.3 Collaborative assessment of the Cultural Heritage Cloud activities and services**

The long-term relevance of the Cultural Heritage Cloud depends not only on technical robustness, but also on its capacity to remain responsive to the evolving needs, practices, and expectations of the communities it is intended to serve in the long run. For this reason, community feedback must be treated not as a one-off consultation exercise, but as a continuous strategic input into the design, prioritisation, development, and assessment of the Cloud’s tools, services, and data ecosystem.

This strategic area sets out a needs-and-objectives strategy (Figure 1) for integrating diverse community feedback into the development and operation of the Cultural Heritage Cloud. Its overall objective is to ensure that digital tools, services, and workflows function as enabling infrastructures for collaboration by continuously capturing user needs, expectations, and feedback, and by aligning technical development with community practices. In this perspective, communities are not only users of the Cloud, but active contributors to its ongoing refinement, helping to shape both what is developed and how its relevance is assessed over time.

Figure 1: Main steps in a needs-and-objectives strategy

SA3 is structured around three complementary priorities. SA3.1 focuses on the active and continuous identification of needs, including barriers, gaps, and emerging expectations relating to tools, services, and data. SA3.2 addresses the translation of these needs into shared objectives and priorities, so that community input can inform strategic direction and planning in a transparent and evidence-based way. SA3.3 focuses on collaborative assessment, ensuring that the value, relevance, and performance of Cloud activities and services are reviewed with communities and that the resulting evidence feeds back into future development cycles.

Across these three priorities, the emphasis is on: the expression of needs before, during, and after use; ongoing feedback loops rather than one-off consultation; sustainability through continuous alignment between users and tools; and capacity-building that enables users and communities not only to understand and use the Cultural Heritage Cloud, but also to contribute to its improvement.

This three-part structure also provides the point of connection between the community-building strategy and the project-level monitoring and assessment framework. D1.3 defines several KPIs that are directly relevant to community building, including community engagement, inclusion of pan-European stakeholders, training and capacity-building, cascading grants, coordination with ECCCH-funded projects, data reuse and enrichment, inclusivity, and metadata enhancement.

SA3 does not establish a separate KPI framework; rather, it clarifies how community needs, feedback, and participation can provide evidence for interpreting these indicators in relation to the actual experience of Cultural Heritage Cloud communities. This connection is further supported by WP9 and the Cloud Assessment Framework, which provides methods, instruments, and data sources for assessing usage, perceived value, community-facing services, and continuous improvement. In this sense, WP4 contributes to the wider assessment cycle by structuring and contextualising community feedback so that it can inform both project-level KPIs and the evaluation processes implemented through WP9.

SA3.1 An active and continuous identification of needs

The first priority of this strategy is to establish a sustained and inclusive process for identifying community needs, barriers, expectations, and gaps. This concerns not only tools and services, but also the data and metadata that underpin the Cultural Heritage Cloud. The objective is to ensure that ECHOES can build and maintain an up-to-date understanding of what different communities require from the Cloud, what limits adoption or effective use, and where unmet needs persist across the ecosystem.

Needs identification should be understood as an ongoing process rather than a discrete stage completed at the beginning of development. Community needs evolve over time, as digital practices change, as new services become available, and as Cultural Heritage Cloud itself grows in scope, maturity, and user base. Accordingly, this strategic priority combines broad consultation with more continuous and low-threshold forms of feedback collection.

The main activities associated with this priority include gathering evidence from communities; identifying difficulties, gaps, and unmet needs; and progressively translating these needs into requirements that can inform subsequent prioritisation and planning, even where not all needs can be addressed within the scope of the Cloud.

- **Feedback from users and non-users**

Focusing only on the Cultural Heritage Cloud users can create a false sense of success. Sometimes, the most valuable insights come from non-users: the people who might want to use the Cloud but are not currently doing so. Understanding the needs of non-users and addressing their barriers and gaps can be just as important as optimising the Cloud for existing users. Getting feedback from users about existing tools and services is easier. Getting feedback from non-users is more challenging. ECHOES should therefore also connect with FAIR and Open Science communities and make use of the sister projects, including the new use-case projects starting in spring 2026.

- **Scope: tools, applications, services, and data**

Data about cultural heritage property is central to the Cloud. Therefore, data-related needs (such as data and metadata quality) are as important as tools' and services' needs, and within the scope of ECHOES' needs-and-objectives strategy. This means the Cloud should both evaluate the quality of the data/metadata but also gather feedback about data/metadata quality needs. It should also anticipate the evolution of such needs, including in relation to the increasing number of AI-based consumers of cultural heritage data.

- **Feedback about *existing* and *missing* features**

The fact that a certain feature exists, or that a given service is provided, does not necessarily mean that it conveniently addresses the needs of its users or potential users. Existing features and services should therefore be continuously re-evaluated. At the same time, stakeholders should be enabled to propose and express demand for missing features. Feature requests relating to vertical applications under development may be handled through existing technical mechanisms, such as GitHub issues, while more general features, or those referring to services or aspects not reflected in a specific repository, will require alternative community-facing mechanisms.

- **Combine *discrete* and *continuous* feedback gathering strategies**

Discrete feedback collection actions (such as major consultations, surveys, pilots and workshops) provide extensive information but, due to the effort required, these are relatively sparse in time. In contrast, continuous feedback mechanisms (such as in-app feedback, logging, and analytics) can provide frequent and up-to-date evidence. A robust needs-identification strategy should combine both approaches. For example, continuous feedback gathered from in-app features can be used to plan surveys or workshops.

- **Specific vs general needs**

The ECHOES consultation already reveals, among other aspects, the major difficulties and barriers in the use of digital tools and services. Some are very specific needs (for example, blockchain functionalities for data traceability, or specific tools for glass-made objects). Others are general, transversal needs (e.g., standardised ontologies and vocabularies, or multilingual support). Both specific and general needs should be gathered to develop a clear picture of adoption barriers and support informed prioritisation and roadmap development.

- **Facilitating feedback collection**

To ensure that the diverse needs of a broad segment of the community are effectively captured, and that this information is gathered and updated continuously as the Cultural Heritage Cloud evolves, it is essential to make feedback mechanisms as accessible and low-effort as possible. This applies both to application developers and service providers, who are responsible for implementing or integrating these mechanisms and sharing the resulting information with ECHOES, and to end users, who should be able to contribute feedback at different levels of effort. These levels should range from very lightweight inputs through intermediate forms of feedback, up to more comprehensive contributions such as full usability evaluations. ECHOES should facilitate the implementation of these feedback collection mechanisms.

- **Capacity-building as a condition for effective participation**

To provide useful contributions and feedback, communities need to understand not only how to use Cultural Heritage Cloud tools and services, but also how they can contribute to their improvement. Capacity-building should therefore be considered an integral part of the needs-and-objectives strategy. Through training, onboarding, and guidance, ECHOES can enable more informed feedback, strengthen participation in co-improvement processes, and support the development of a shared language across communities.

- **Reporting detected needs**

Given the wide diversity of projects, initiatives, and stakeholders involved, it is essential to share and disseminate the needs identified by ECHOES, sister projects, and other related initiatives, which represent gaps/barriers in the daily work of cultural heritage professionals. ECHOES can play a key role by centralising the compilation, analysis, and publication of feedback related to community needs, thus building a shared understanding of common challenges, avoiding fragmentation, and maximising reuse across the projects.

- **A collaborative strategy for translating needs into requirements**

Once identified in the previous steps, translating identified needs into concrete requirements for the technical development of the Cloud's infrastructure, tools and services is a critical step in the process, and one that is far from trivial. Some high-level barriers, such as those referring to lack of interoperability or insufficient training, are well known and widely acknowledged.

However, addressing them in an effective way remains challenging. Other needs may be more specific or domain-oriented, for example, related to advanced data traceability mechanisms or workflows tailored to specific heritage domains. Even in these cases, converting such needs into well-scoped requirements can be complex, as they often involve implicit assumptions and heterogeneous practices across domains and communities.

The strategy is based on the principle that the translation of needs into requirements must be carried out as a collaborative, iterative, and evidence-based process. It should involve relevant stakeholders across domains, including end users, domain specialists, and technical partners, to ensure that requirements are both meaningful and feasible. To this end, identified needs should be progressively consolidated, discussed, refined, and then translated into requirements that are validated against project objectives and implementation constraints. Needs should also be distinguished according to implementation feasibility, as some may remain out of scope for the Cloud.

- **Strategic use of beta testers and early adopters**

Beta testers and early adopters are essential in the early stages of the Cultural Heritage Cloud, before a critical mass of users is reached. Beyond technical testing and usability feedback, these profiles can play a key role in validating assumptions and informing prioritisation decisions. Their early engagement helps assess whether tools and services address real needs and guides the development roadmaps.

- **The private business sector as a contributor to feedback-driven innovation**

Beyond the traditional private actors active in the field of cultural heritage, such as private conservator-restorers and archaeologists, businesses from the ICT and CCIs sectors should be recognised not only as potential providers of resources and services for the Cultural Heritage Cloud, but also as important contributors to continuous feedback loops. Their contribution is not mainly expected in relation to the testing of existing Cloud applications, but rather in assessing and improving the enabling conditions for integration and innovation across the Cloud ecosystem, including APIs, interoperability mechanisms, semantic frameworks, onboarding processes, and the ease with which new applications and services can be integrated into the Cloud. As these actors are also expected to play a key role in developing and providing new resources, such as tools or training material, for the Cloud, they can benefit significantly from the feedback collected from heritage communities. Their participation in these processes can help align technological development with user needs and operational requirements.

- **Mechanisms for fostering and recognising participation in testing and feedback activities**

Participation in testing, validation, and feedback activities should be actively encouraged and recognised as a strategic component of community building. As these activities require time, effort, and expertise, ECHOES should establish mechanisms that both incentivise engagement and acknowledge the value of user contributions. These may include early access to technical developments, opportunities to influence feature design and priorities, digital badges and public recognition, and, where appropriate, access to training, networking, or showcase opportunities. Such measures can help reduce barriers to participation, strengthen users' sense of ownership, and support the transition from occasional feedback providers to active contributors to the evolution of the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

- **Ambassador-type approaches for community outreach and feedback mediation**

New Ambassador-type approaches can strengthen the identification of needs by extending ECHOES' reach into national, thematic, and professional communities. Trusted individuals embedded in these contexts help promote awareness of the Cultural Heritage Cloud, encourage participation in consultations and testing, identify needs and barriers from underrepresented groups, and communicate project priorities and opportunities back to their communities. In this way, ambassadors can support more continuous and distributed feedback collection while also helping translate local or domain-specific perspectives into a shared framework for collaboration.

SA3.2 Community-backed objectives

The second priority of this strategy is to ensure that the needs identified through community engagement are not left at the level of dispersed observations but are translated into a coherent strategic direction. This requires the consolidation of needs, gaps, pain points, and derived requirements into a limited set of community-backed objectives that can guide planning, prioritisation, and future assessment with the Cloud governance framework (D10.2).²⁴

The purpose of this stage is not to define detailed technical solutions. Rather, it is to provide a shared strategic framework that expresses where the Cultural Heritage Cloud is expected to generate value for communities and against which progress can later be monitored.

²⁴ Petitcol, R., *et al.* (2026) *Governance Model of the legal entity (D10.2)*.

In this sense, SA3.2 connects community consultation to decision-making by establishing objectives that are both evidence-based and broadly accepted by the communities whose needs they are intended to address.

The main activities associated with this priority include synthesising outputs from needs identification; defining a limited set of high-level, community-oriented objectives; translating these into a small number of indicators; validating the objectives and indicators with representative community stakeholders; and maintaining them as a shared reference for subsequent prioritisation and planning.

This process should also remain aligned with the relevant ECHOES and Cultural Heritage Cloud coordination, technical, and assessment bodies. Community-backed objectives and indicators should therefore be discussed, where appropriate, with the bodies responsible for integration, assessment, and governance, including the ECHOES Integration Task Force, WP9 through the Cloud Assessment Framework, and the relevant advisory or governance structures foreseen for the Cloud. This ensures that community feedback is connected to the technical evaluation, prioritisation, and decision-making processes through which the Cloud evolves.

Principles for defining objectives

- **From identified needs to strategic direction**

This stage translates the consolidated outputs of SA3.1 into a limited set of high-level, community-oriented objectives. These objectives should express the broad areas in which the Cultural Heritage Cloud is expected to generate value for communities, such as access, storage, processing, interoperability, and capacity-building.

- **Maintain a high level of abstraction**

Objectives at this stage should remain strategic rather than operational. Their purpose is to provide a stable reference framework for subsequent prioritisation, planning, and assessment, while remaining broad enough to accommodate different communities, use cases, and implementation pathways.

- **Use a small set of robust indicators**

Each objective should be associated with a limited number of indicators to support monitoring over time and comparison across assessment cycles, combining quantitative and qualitative evidence where appropriate. In line with ESFRI recommendations, indicators should be designed to satisfy both the SMART logic (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound) and the RACER criteria (Relevant, Accepted, Credible, Easy to monitor, and Robust).

ESFRI's monitoring guidance presents RACER as a quality standard for KPIs and links it to a dialogue-based process for defining appropriate indicators.

- **Ensure stakeholder validation and acceptance**

The definition of objectives and indicators should be coordinated by ECHOES – and later on by the Cloud governance framework – but validated with representative community stakeholders. This is important not only to confirm relevance, but also to ensure that the resulting indicators are accepted by the communities whose needs they are intended to reflect, consistent with the RACER approach. This validation should involve both cultural heritage professionals and ICT developers.

- **Keep the process iterative**

This stage should be repeated periodically, in alignment with broader integration and assessment cycles, so that objectives and indicators can be reviewed considering evolving community needs, technical developments, and emerging evidence from use and feedback.

SA3.3 Collaborative prioritisation and assessment of the Cultural Heritage Cloud activities, tools and services

The third priority of this strategy is to ensure that community feedback is not only used to identify needs and define objectives, but also to assess the relevance and effectiveness of the Cultural Heritage Cloud as it evolves. Collaborative assessment closes the feedback loop by linking community experience, evidence of use, and strategic review. In this way, assessment becomes a shared process through which the Cloud can monitor whether it is meeting its objectives, identify new barriers or opportunities, and revise its priorities over time.

Within the broader needs-and-objectives lifecycle, this priority is closely connected to prioritisation and planning, and to the assessment processes supported elsewhere in the project. While the detailed implementation of the Cloud Assessment Framework is addressed in WP9, SA3 emphasises the strategic role of communities in providing feedback for the continuous evaluation of the Cloud digital ecosystem and in ensuring that assessment results inform future planning and development.

The main activities associated with this priority include prioritising needs and objectives using transparent criteria; defining and maintaining a development roadmap aligned with agreed priorities; identifying responsible and contributing actors; disseminating the roadmap as a shared planning instrument; and ensuring that evidence from use and assessment informs subsequent revisions.

Principles for prioritisation, planning, and collaborative assessment

- **Impact- and feasibility-based prioritisation**

Prioritisation should be guided by a balanced assessment of expected impact on the community and implementation feasibility. The expected contribution of each objective to addressing community needs and strengthening the long-term relevance of the Cultural Heritage Cloud should be considered alongside factors such as technical complexity, maturity, dependencies, timing, and resource constraints. This approach helps ensure that prioritisation remains transparent, evidence-based, and strategically grounded.

- **Alignment with existing prioritisation principles**

For *existing* resources that could be integrated into the Cloud, prioritisation should align, where relevant, with the Core Prioritisation Principles set out in D3.1:²⁵ (a) Community Priorities: resources must respond to known needs identified within the community; (b) Technical Readiness: priority is given to stable, well-documented, and maintained resources rather than simple proofs of concept; (c) Architectural Coherence: integration decisions should consider the overall Cultural Heritage Cloud architecture, specifically evaluating how a resource fits within the ecosystem; (d) Long-term Sustainability: explicit maintenance responsibilities must be assigned to the resource provider. The strategy should also favour open resources, though proprietary resources are not excluded if their conditions of use are clearly stated and managed.

- **Use of MoSCoW methodology**

In line with D3.2,²⁶ integration units may be categorised to manage the workflow and support prioritisation: (a) Must Have: strategically imperative integrations critical to core Cultural Heritage Cloud objectives, including, for example, outputs from sister projects; (b) Should Have: highly desirable integrations that enhance usability or collaboration but are not time-critical; (c) Could Have: resources that add value or innovation but are not essential for short-term operations; (d) Won't Have (for now): integrations that are unjustified due to low impact or missing technical dependencies.

²⁵ Kotzinos, D., et al. (2024) *Integration Strategy for datasets, tools and workflows with potential for reuse in ECHOES (D3.1)*.

²⁶ Chambers, S. et al. (2025) *ECHOES Integration Roadmap (D3.2)*.

- **The development of an open roadmap as a shared planning instrument**

The main output of this stage should be an open roadmap that translates prioritised objectives into a coherent plan over time. The roadmap should provide a shared reference framework indicating which developments are expected to be pursued, supported, or enabled, and under which broad timeframe and responsibility structure.

- **Recognition of multiple implementation pathways**

Addressing prioritised needs may involve different types of actors and mechanisms, including (a) development by ECHOES technical partners, (b) orientation of ECHOES cascading grant calls, (c) contributions from sister projects and their cascading projects, (d) engagement of commercial actors and external developers, and (e) national and international initiatives such as Data Space for Cultural Heritage. Accordingly, the roadmap may include both approved or planned tools, applications, features, and services, as well as identified needs for which external contributions are encouraged, or policy-level prioritisation (European or national) is recommended.

- **Project-level coordination and alignment**

At the project level, the ECHOES governance structure, including ECHOES Integration Task Force (EITF), the Stakeholder Council and the advisory boards, ensures that the community needs identified in WP4 and their associated objectives are consistently prioritised, translated into a suitable development plan, and communicated to the teams responsible for implementation, including ECHOES developer teams, cascading/sister projects, and made open for other potential contributors.

- **A living and revisable roadmap**

The roadmap should be maintained as a living document, subject to periodic review and update. Revisions should reflect progress in implementation, new evidence emerging from community feedback, and changes in technical feasibility or strategic context. This will help ensure that planning remains responsive, realistic, and aligned with the evolving needs of the community.

Broader needs-and-objectives lifecycle context

For completeness, the broader needs-and-objectives lifecycle also includes implementation and formal assessment stages (Figure 1) that are closely connected to this strategic area, even if they are not defined here in detail.

Implementation of prioritised tools, services, and features

This stage covers the execution of the development roadmap by the different actors involved. Implementation may take place through multiple pathways, including development by ECHOES technical partners, cascading projects, sister projects, and external contributors. At the project level, the EITF plays a key role in coordinating efforts and integrating results from other projects into the Cloud.

Assessment facilitated by WP9

This stage closes the loop by leveraging the evaluation framework and tools provided by WP9 to support continuous assessment and feedback collection across the Cultural Heritage Cloud ecosystem. WP9 enables the systematic monitoring of usage, performance, and user-perceived value, for example, through frequency of use, user ratings, and qualitative feedback, ensuring that evidence from real use feeds back into needs identification, objective revision, and roadmap updates.

***Lessons learned from:* Illustrative examples of the needs-and-objectives strategy**

The following illustrative examples are intended to show how community feedback can inform the full needs-and-objectives cycle, from the identification of unmet needs to the definition of objectives, prioritisation of actions, implementation pathways, and subsequent assessment.

Example 1: Advanced 3D processing tools

- **Needs identification:** Feedback reveals unmet needs for advanced 3D processing, such as segmentation, analysis, simulation, and support for moving cultural heritage objects, beyond basic annotation functionalities. At present, these needs are often addressed through external commercial tools that are poorly integrated with the Cultural Heritage Cloud. ECHOES and its sister projects do not have the capacity to cover the full range of these needs directly.
- **Objectives:** An objective is defined to increase coverage of advanced 3D processing needs by enabling the participation of private-sector providers, while allowing them to preserve license-based revenue models.
- **Prioritisation and planning:** The development roadmap prioritises the creation of a Cultural Heritage Cloud marketplace with a dedicated category for advanced 3D processing tools, complemented by capacity-building actions and targeted communication to attract private providers.

- Implementation: The marketplace, onboarding mechanisms, and supporting services are implemented by ECHOES and contributing actors, with private companies integrating and publishing their open-source tools on the Cloud.
- Assessment: WP9-enabled evaluation tracks indicators such as the number of participating companies, the number of available tools and services, active users, and newly covered needs, feeding the results back into the continuous improvement cycle.

Example 2: Multilingual support for regional heritage professionals

- Needs identification: Feedback from regional and local heritage professionals indicates that limited language support in key entry points of the Cultural Heritage Cloud, such as onboarding, documentation, search, and metadata authoring tools, represents a major barrier to adoption.
- Objectives: An objective is defined to improve accessibility for regional heritage communities by providing multilingual support in selected, high-impact Cloud components, focusing on onboarding processes, core documentation, and metadata-related services.
- Prioritisation and planning: The development roadmap prioritises multilingual onboarding workflows, guidance for multilingual metadata creation, and search functionalities supporting multiple languages, while explicitly excluding full localisation of all applications and services.
- Implementation: Targeted multilingual features are implemented in the prioritised Cloud components by ECHOES and contributing projects, supported by capacity-building actions tailored to regional heritage professionals.
- Assessment: WP9-enabled evaluation tracks adoption by targeted language communities, usage of multilingual entry points, and perceived reduction of language-related barriers to adoption, feeding the results into iterative refinements.

Rationale for private sector engagement

Within this Strategic Area, private sector actors play a key role as contributors to continuous feedback loops, supporting the iterative development of Cloud tools and services. Through their involvement as early adopters, beta testers, and service providers, they generate practical insights into usability, interoperability, and operational constraints.

These contributions are particularly relevant in addressing challenges identified in the ECHOES consultation (D4.1), such as integration complexity, cost barriers, and the need for more user-friendly and interoperable solutions. By providing structured feedback based on real-world applications, private actors support the alignment of technological development with user needs and operational requirements.

Concrete participation opportunities for companies include:

- Supporting activities in the Cloud Assessment (WP9), including recruiting pilot participants, refining user profiles, and feeding the continuous improvement cycle implemented by WP9.

Strategic Area 4: Towards a common language: sharing languages and concepts through the Cultural Heritage Cloud

Objective:

The fourth Strategic Area aims to strengthen effective cross-domain and multilingual collaboration within the Cultural Heritage Cloud by promoting shared reference concepts, semantic alignment and coordination of multilingual resources, while building existing project assets and established initiatives.

Key emphasis:

- Common conceptual ground for collaboration
- Strategic approach to multilingualism
- Building on existing assets and experiences

SA4 is therefore composed of:

- **SA4.1 Fostering interdisciplinary dialogue within Digital Commons**
- **SA4.2 Building a multilingual Cultural Heritage Cloud**
- **SA4.3 Enabling the adoption and sharing of reference concepts**

Establishing a common understanding through language is the fundamental prerequisite for the digital transformation of the European cultural heritage sector, which is currently hindered by fragmented priorities and siloed practices.²⁷ Language, in the context of the Cultural Heritage Cloud, should be understood in a broad and inclusive sense. It refers, first, to natural languages and therefore to the need for multilingual access, participation, and knowledge exchange across European and international heritage communities. At the same time, it also refers to the domain-specific languages through which cultural heritage actors describe, organise, and interpret knowledge, including specialised terminologies, vocabularies, metadata schemas, and conceptual frameworks used in different disciplines, professions, and institutional settings. Building a common language for the Cultural Heritage Cloud, therefore, does not mean reducing this diversity but creating the conditions under which linguistic and conceptual diversity can be shared, aligned, and made interoperable, so that communities can collaborate across languages, domains, and practices.

This section outlines how the community building strategy can be reinforced through a methodology for adopting a common “language” among communities and across communities. Drawing on the information obtained from engaged communities (Task 4.1) and networks (Knowledge Pillar), two resources have been created:

- (a) an inventory of broadly used terminologies, vocabularies, metadata schemas, and conceptual frameworks, taking into account the different linguistic, disciplinary and cultural practices, as well as
- b) a set of recommendations to be used in T7.4.1 to overcome language and discipline barriers, to foster connections across different fields, and to ensure multilingual and aligned metadata.

SA4.1: Fostering interdisciplinary dialogue within Digital Commons

Semantic artefacts provide the semantic backbone for the Cultural Heritage Cloud. Without them, data produced by different institutions, disciplines, and language communities remains trapped in local silos, maybe consistent within each system, but invisible and unusable across them. This section sets out the conceptual foundation, strategic principles, and practical actions through which ECHOES can build and sustain a semantic infrastructure that facilitates cross-institutional collaboration

²⁷ Tasovac, T., et al. (2024) *Principles for capacity-building (D5.1)*.

Clarifying the Key Concepts: Knowledge Organisation Systems versus Semantic Artefacts

Two related but distinct terms structure discussions in this field, and it is worth clarifying them before providing an overview of the current initiatives.

Knowledge Organisation Systems (KOS) is a broad, well-established term, especially in library and documentation contexts, covering resources that organise and structure knowledge, such as controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, thesauri, classification systems, and ontologies.²⁸ These resources help communities describe concepts consistently and make information easier to find, compare, and connect. The [Getty vocabularies](#) are a widely used example in the cultural heritage domain because they support consistent description and retrieval of cultural heritage objects, artworks, places and related information across institutions.

Semantic artefact is a more recent term introduced by FAIRsFAIR (2020) in digital and open science contexts and adopted in the EOSC Interoperability Framework.²⁹ It refers to a machine-readable model of knowledge, such as a controlled vocabulary, thesaurus, or ontology, designed to support the annotation, extraction, representation, and linking of knowledge within datasets.

The key distinction between these two concepts lies in the fact that “semantic artefact” places greater emphasis on the fact that these resources are designed not only for human use, but also for sharing, alignment, reuse, and processing by digital systems.

For the purposes of the Cultural Heritage Cloud, “semantic artefact” is the preferred term throughout this document, as it better reflects the machine-actionable, interoperability requirements of the Cloud infrastructure. In this context, semantic artefacts can therefore be understood as formal, machine-actionable representations of knowledge that define concepts and their relationships within the heritage domain. They include ontologies, controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, thesauri, and metadata schemas, and they provide the common structure needed to connect heterogeneous data coming from different institutions, disciplines, and national contexts. In this sense, they form part of the semantic backbone of the digital ecosystem, enabling systems and communities to work with shared or aligned meanings even when their practices, languages, and documentation traditions differ. A well-known example is CIDOC CRM,³⁰ the international ISO standard that supports the semantic integration of cultural heritage information across museums, archives, libraries, and research environments.

²⁸ Hodge, G. (2000) *Systems of knowledge organisation for digital libraries: beyond traditional authority files*.

²⁹ Nyberg Åkerström, W., et al. (2024) *Developing and implementing the semantic interoperability recommendations of the EOSC Interoperability Framework*.

³⁰ Doerr, M. (2003) 'The CIDOC conceptual reference module: an ontological approach to semantic interoperability of metadata'.

Role of Semantic Artefacts in the Cultural Heritage Cloud

More specifically, within the Cultural Heritage Cloud, semantic artefacts play an important role across three interrelated dimensions:

- Enabling interoperability through shared conceptual structures such as CIDOC CRM and the Heritage Digital Twin Ontology (D6.1),³¹ and through the alignment of different professional vocabularies and knowledge sharing practices across domains, as discussed in D5.1.³²
- Facilitating multilingualism through SKOS-based vocabularies. SKOS is an interoperable format which supports multilingual labelling, cross-lingual discovery, and semantic alignment across languages. This also enables the structuring of cultural heritage data as knowledge graphs, revealing relationships between heritage assets, historical events, places, and other relevant entities that would otherwise remain invisible across language boundaries
- Ensuring that the Cultural Heritage Cloud data remains findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, in line with the FAIR principles.³³

These three dimensions are mutually reinforcing. Progress on any one of them strengthens the others, which is why semantic artefact must be treated as a strategic investment rather than a technical side task.

Best Practices for Developing and Publishing Multilingual Semantic Artefacts

Publishing multilingual semantic artefacts is not simply a matter of choosing a format, but of organising a durable socio-technical process that sustains the artefact through its full lifecycle, i.e. from initial design through community adoption, versioning, and long-term maintenance.

Past and current initiatives inform the approach adopted in ECHOES. Experience from the Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project showed that language technologies can support multilingual terminology building and SKOS publication, but also that expert review and validation remain indispensable, especially when multilingual labels and automatically assisted workflows are involved.³⁴

³¹ Sielli, A., *et al.* (2026) *CH knowledge base – Data Strategy (D6.1)*.

³² Tasovac, T., *et al.* (2024) *Principles for capacity-building (D5.1)*.

³³ Wilkinson, *et al.* (2016) 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship'.

³⁴ Gamba, F., *et al.* (2022) 'Language technologies for the creation of multilingual terminologies: lessons learned from the SSHOC project'.

More recent work in the heritage domain has further stressed that FAIR semantic artefacts require explicit lifecycle management, including editorial policies, provenance, versioning, validation procedures, stable identifiers at both vocabulary and concept level, and publication in infrastructures that support discovery, access, and reuse over time.^{35 36}

Synthesising these perspectives, the following best practices can be applied to the development and sharing of multilingual CH semantic artefacts:

- Adopt a community-driven approach to vocabulary development, governed by the communities that use the artefacts, with explicit roles for domain experts, data stewards, and multilingual reviewers. Governance structures must be established before vocabulary development and publication to ensure a systematic approach.
- Set up a clear governance and validation workflows through documented editorial policies, validation procedures, update triggers, deprecation rules, and language version responsibilities.
- Use SKOS as the interoperability baseline through formal representation of semantic artefacts in SKOS format, using standard properties (skos:prefLabel, skos:definition, skos:broader, dcterms:source) ensuring compatibility with the semantic web and downstream alignment tools.
- Apply systematic linking and alignment with external resources (e.g. CIDOC CRM, Getty AAT, Wikidata) using SKOS mapping properties or OWL equivalences, with alignment decisions documented, versioned and validated by domain experts.
- Publish the semantic artefacts available and accessible through a federated infrastructure, such as OntoPortal-based catalogues or SKOS-oriented publication environments, with machine-readable metadata, stable URIs, open licences, so that vocabularies are discoverable both as whole resources and at the level of individual concepts.

These principles informed the methodological approach adopted in ECHOES and were concretely applied in the design of the ECHOES Glossary (described in §SA4.2), which was conceived not merely as an internal terminology list, but as a governed, multilingual semantic artefact embedded in an explicit editorial and publication workflow.

³⁵ Guillem, A., *et al.* (forthcoming 2026) 'Managing the thesaurus data cycle as a FAIR semantic artefact for heritage science'.

³⁶ Scarpa, E., *et al.* (2025) *⟨H/RADIOSA⟩: recommended approaches for the development of interoperable open semantic artefacts in the heritage domain.*

Inventorying existing cultural heritage semantic artefacts

Current State of the Art

ECHOES has started building an inventory of existing and widely used cultural heritage semantic artefacts based on inputs collected in WP3 and WP4. The current inventory covers 45 semantic artefacts and provides information about the name of the resource, URL, description, sub-domain, available languages, type of KOS and contributors.

The purpose of the inventory was to identify reference resources that can support reuse, alignment, and cross-domain interoperability within the Cultural Heritage Cloud. The inventory is not published yet and it has a structural limitation that it shares with the broader EOSC landscape: findability is currently possible only at the vocabulary level. Users need to browse artefacts individually to locate specific concepts and definitions, a process that is inefficient and time-consuming, discouraging reuse of the inventory.

Enriching the Inventory through External Alignment

This ECHOES inventory should be consolidated and enriched through alignment with external initiatives that are already addressing semantic artefact discovery and documentation in the heritage domain. A particularly relevant example is [H-SeTIS](#) (Heritage – Semantic Tools and Interoperability Survey), a curated database that covers five resource types: ontologies, metadata standards, thesauri, application profiles, and software tools implementing semantic artefacts; it also includes a reviewed bibliography maintained as a public resource.³⁷

Aligning the current ECHOES inventory of semantic artefacts with H-SeTIS and related cataloguing initiatives would transform it from an internal working list into a community-maintained reference resource that can survive the project.

Liaising with EOSC-related Initiatives

Furthermore, ECHOES should actively liaise with ongoing EOSC-related initiatives, including the work of the OSCARS Task Force on EOSC Glossaries, where recent discussions led by CLARIN, revealed that findability at the level of the individual concept or term is a prerequisite for semantic linking and integrated ecosystem development (Broeder et al., 2025).³⁸

³⁷ Scarpa, E. and Valente, R. (2025) *Heritage — semantic tools and interoperability survey bibliography*.

Another relevant initiative, although not CH specific, is the ATRIUM ‘Overview of Models and Formats in the Field’, which covers over 130 semantic artefacts across four EU research infrastructures (DARIAH, ARIADNE, CLARIN, OPERAS).

³⁸ Broeder, D., et al. (2025) ‘Terminology infrastructure for EOSC: enhanced findability of semantic artefacts’.

The initiative explores the importance of harmonised metadata, interoperability across catalogues, and the ability to search both vocabulary descriptions and vocabulary contents through infrastructures such as OntoPortal, BARTOC, and FAIRsharing.

By taking into consideration the above initiatives and linking with them, ECHOES can improve the visibility, interoperability, and long-term reuse of cultural heritage semantic artefacts across a broader cross-domain environment.

SA4.2: Building a multilingual Cultural Heritage Cloud

Developing FAIR multilingual semantic artefacts within the cultural heritage cloud is essential for enabling interoperable, reusable and cross-border access to cultural heritage data. Moreover, multilingual semantic artefacts support inclusive access, facilitate international collaboration, and enable advanced digital services such as semantic search, linked data integration, and AI-driven analysis within the CH ecosystem.

The ECHOES Glossary (see D4.1)³⁹ is presented here as an example of an interoperable and multilingual semantic resource built and maintained by the Cultural Heritage Cloud community. It was developed as a first step to establish a shared language within the ECHOES community (including sister projects), providing a common reference framework for communication, collaboration, and reporting activities. The first version of the glossary can be consulted [here](#).

Its workflow and management model are aligned with the requirements for FAIR semantic artefacts, as described in the literature on multilingual terminology and thesaurus lifecycle management.^{40 41} In this perspective, FAIRness is not understood as a purely technical property, but as the result of explicit governance, documented processes, and appropriate infrastructure support throughout the glossary's lifecycle.

A Git-based environment will be set up and used to document and support these processes, including the addition of new concepts and new language versions. Crucially, the communities using the Cultural Heritage Cloud, including the ECHOES sister projects, must collaborate to maintain the various language versions aligned

³⁹ Prandoni, C., *et al.* (2026) *Report on identification of communities and their needs (D4.1)*.

⁴⁰ Gamba, F., *et al.* (2022) 'Language technologies for the creation of multilingual terminologies: lessons learned from the SSHOC project'.

⁴¹ Jonquet, C. *et al.* (2026) 'Federated FAIR semantic artefacts discovery and search with OntoPortal federation'.

The FAIR dimensions are implemented as follows:

- Findability is ensured by structuring each concept as an identifiable entity within a SKOS model, with clear preferred labels, multilingual variants, and documented sources. The Glossary is conceived as a reusable and citable resource, in which both the overall artefact and individual concepts can be persistently referenced.
- Accessibility is supported using open standards, machine-readable formats, and clear source attribution, guaranteeing that both human users and information systems can retrieve and interpret the content without ambiguity or technical barriers.
- Interoperability is achieved through formal modelling in SKOS and the use of standard properties such as `skos:prefLabel`, `skos:definition`, `skos:broader`, and `dcterms:source`. This ensures compatibility with semantic web technologies and enables alignment with other vocabularies, ontologies, and data infrastructures.
- Reusability is reinforced by explicit provenance of documentation, transparent editorial policies, multilingual coverage, and versioning practices that preserve referential stability over time. The glossary's governance framework, including validation of workflows and community feedback mechanisms, further strengthens trust and contextual intelligibility, which are essential conditions for meaningful reuse.

By embedding these principles into its editorial and publication workflow, the Glossary satisfies the core requisites of a FAIR semantic artefact. FAIRness emerges not simply from compliance with SKOS, but from the explicit management of responsibilities, lifecycle stages, documentation, and community engagement that sustain the glossary as a durable, intelligible, and reusable semantic resource.

While this resource is mainly for internal use by the project members and cannot replace other semantic artefacts, it will be integrated into the ECHOES semantic ecosystem, especially within the HDTO (see D7.1).

SA4.3: Enabling the adoption and sharing of reference concepts

The Strategic Challenge

From a community building perspective, enabling the adoption and sharing of reference concepts is essential for making collaboration sustainable across disciplines, institutions, and language communities. The challenge is not only to make semantic resources available, but also to ensure that communities are supported in understanding them, relating them to their own practices, and progressively aligning their vocabularies and conceptual models with shared frameworks. In this sense, reference concepts function as mediating tools that help communities communicate across differences without requiring the loss of local specificity or domain expertise.

Within ECHOES, our community building activities should also support the adoption and development of the Heritage Digital Twin Ontology (HDTO, WP7). This collaboration will help ensure that communities are not only provided with shared semantic resources, but also with guidance and good practices for concept mapping, vocabulary alignment, multilingual extension, and semantic interoperability. The aim is to support a gradual and community-sensitive process through which existing vocabularies can become more interoperable and reusable within the wider Cultural Heritage Cloud ecosystem. Related initiatives already illustrate the value of such an approach.

For example, the [RICHeS Heritage Science Modelling](#) work develops CIDOC CRM-aligned models to support documentation, interoperability, and FAIR-oriented data sharing in ways that can help communities converge around shared conceptual references while maintaining their own domain perspectives. In this perspective, SA4.3 contributes to community building by creating the conceptual conditions for collaboration, mutual understanding, and knowledge exchange across the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

The Findability Problem

A prerequisite for the adoption of reference concepts is discoverability. Locating and accessing semantic artefacts remains a significant challenge to effective collaboration across disciplines and the reuse of data and services. Scientific communities often describe their datasets, tools or services using different vocabularies and metadata standards, sometimes using different versions, proprietary vocabularies, or none at all. Additionally, inconsistencies, duplication, and ambiguity within and between semantic artefacts create barriers to interoperability and hinder the development of shared standards.

The OSCARS Task Force on EOSC Glossaries (Broeder, D. et al., 2025)⁴² characterises the above-described challenge as semantic fragmentation, meaning that terminological diversity in describing data and services and use of disparate vocabularies by scientific communities leads to a situation where data and services across disciplines cannot be reliably connected. The ECHOES KOS inventory, developed in Task 4.1, illustrates this limitation directly: users must browse vocabularies individually to locate concepts and definitions, making the process inefficient and time-consuming.

The critical insight from the OSCARS analysis report is that findability must be ensured not only at the vocabulary level but at the level of the individual concept or term. Vocabulary-level metadata is insufficient for most practical reuse decisions: researchers and data stewards need to inspect actual concept definitions, hierarchical relations, term notes, and multilingual labels before they can determine whether a given artefact is appropriate for their needs.

⁴² Broeder, D., et al. (2025) 'Terminology infrastructure for EOSC: enhanced findability of semantic artefacts'.

Strategic Actions for the Cultural Heritage Cloud

The OSCARS Task Force identifies four strategic actions relevant to any EOSC-aligned semantic infrastructure. Each has direct implications for the Cultural Heritage Cloud:

- Establish a minimum common metadata standard for describing semantic artefacts, to facilitate cross-catalogue search, alignment, and interoperability.
- Map and analyse overlaps among vocabularies to identify integration opportunities and reduce redundancy. This requires a systematic mapping exercise across Cultural Heritage Cloud vocabularies, such as those listed in the KOS inventory, produced in Task 4.1, and integration of the vocabularies into the ECHOES Knowledge Base.
- Register the ECHOES KOS inventory of existing Cultural Heritage Cloud semantic artefacts in external catalogues such as the domain-specific H-SeTIS database and/or interdisciplinary registries such as [FAIRsharing](#), [BARTOC](#), or [Linked Open Vocabularies \(LOV\)](#) as an immediate discoverability baseline.
- Pursue the integration of the ECHOES Glossary and other semantic artefacts produced in the project with an [OntoPortal](#) instance to enable granular, concept-level search and discovery.
- Develop and implement policy and governance frameworks that ensure effective onboarding, curation, maintenance, and long-term sustainability of semantic artefacts and their hosting platforms.

By adopting these measures, the Cultural Heritage Cloud will align with broader EOSC objectives and significantly enhance the usability and impact of its semantic artefacts.

Rationale for private sector engagement

Within this Strategic Area, private sector actors contribute as semantic and technical enablers of interoperability, multilingual access, and the practical adoption of shared reference concepts. By participating as service providers, developers, and operational partners, they can support cultural heritage organisations in preparing, enriching, aligning, translating, and publishing data and metadata in ways that make them reusable within the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

Through practical experience in digitisation, data management, metadata enrichment, terminology services, software development, and interoperability, private actors can help lower barriers to the adoption of shared semantic resources. In doing so, they support the use of multilingual vocabularies, semantic artefacts, and reference concepts across different institutional, linguistic, and disciplinary contexts.

Concrete participation opportunities for companies include:

- Supporting cultural heritage organisations in metadata enrichment, vocabulary alignment, terminology management, and semantic mapping.
- Developing or integrating tools and services for multilingual access, semantic interoperability, concept-level search, and data discovery.
- Helping institutions prepare datasets, vocabularies, and semantic resources for publication, linking, reuse, and long-term accessibility through the Cloud.

Next steps and future updates of the strategy

The present strategy provides a framework for community building within ECHOES during the current phase of the project. Building on the results of Task 4.1 and aligned with the objectives of Task 4.2, it consolidates the main strategic directions through which the project approaches the formation of the Cultural Heritage Cloud community, strengthening individual agency and collaboration, relying on existing organisations and networks, integrating community needs and feedback into the development of the Cloud, and fostering a common conceptual and multilingual basis for cooperation across domains. In this sense, the present strategy paper can be understood as the main reference point for the next phase of WP4 activities, establishing the principles, priorities, and areas of action.

The presented strategy paper is therefore focused on testing, applying, and consolidating this framework through subsequent project activities. The continuation of community building efforts following the proposed framework includes the implementation of the community building strategy, the further development of the Cultural Heritage Cloud Charter, and the preparation of a strategy for the growth of the community. A first draft of the Cultural Heritage Cloud Community Charter is included in Annex 2 as a preliminary working basis for this next phase. The draft translates the community building principles discussed in this strategy into a concise set of community-facing values, including participation and collaboration, openness and transparency, accessibility and inclusivity, interoperability, and long-term stewardship. It is not presented as a final governance document, but as a starting point to be further discussed, refined, and aligned with the relevant ECHOES activities and governance-related deliverables.

Next steps and updates will give the strategy paper a clear role within the wider structure of ECHOES, which will be to define the shared strategic basis upon which future actions can be organised, coordinated, and assessed. The strategy developed here is therefore intended to guide the practical translation of the project's community building objectives into concrete forms of engagement, coordination, and participation across the later stages of the action.

A first priority in the next phase will be the progressive operationalisation of the four strategic areas identified in this document. This means, first, reinforcing the social and organisational conditions that enable collaboration by connecting community building activities with capacity-building, mutual learning, and the recognition of individual agency within collective processes. Second, it means using the consortium's existing links with professional organisations, umbrella bodies, and partner networks as the main channels through which the Cultural Heritage Cloud community can continue to expand in a structured and credible manner.

Third, it requires the practical establishment of feedback mechanisms through which communities can express needs, validate priorities, and contribute to the continuous assessment of tools, services, and data. Fourth, it involves carrying forward the work on multilingualism, semantic alignment, and shared reference concepts so that collaboration across disciplines, sectors, and language communities is supported by an increasingly coherent common framework.

In this perspective, the next stage should be understood as the implementation phase of the strategy articulated in the strategy document. More specifically, the activities that follow will provide the opportunity to test whether the strategic priorities defined here can effectively support different forms of participation across the Cloud ecosystem, including engagement through existing networks, targeted community activation, structured feedback collection, and the alignment of community expectations with the evolving technical and organisational dimensions of the Cultural Heritage Cloud. This is effectively an implementation phase, which is essential in order to move from a strategic framework to an embedded mode of operation, where community building is treated as a constitutive dimension of the Cloud's development and use.

A second priority will be to ensure that the strategy remains closely connected to the broader project's architecture. Community building in ECHOES is designed to follow up with communication and dissemination activities, integration and collaboration work, capacity-building activities, the assessment framework developed through the project, the governance, and the sustainability perspectives of ECHOES. This cross-project alignment will be necessary to ensure that community engagement remains linked to the actual development of services, workflows, semantic resources, and participation structures within the Cloud, and that the strategic priorities identified in this document are translated into project-wide practices.

The project's subsequent tasks already indicate several concrete directions for this transition. As specified in the Description of the Action, the implementation phase will include the preparation of an implementation plan to strengthen and develop the Cultural Heritage Cloud community, the further elaboration of the Charter for the Cloud, and the design of a strategy for community growth and expansion. Together, these activities provide the natural continuation of the present strategy. At the same time, the practical implementation of the strategy will also provide a basis for its future consolidation. The later stages of the project will make it possible to assess how the principles and directions set out here function in practice, how they interact with the wider ECHOES ecosystem, and where further clarification, prioritisation, or adaptation may be required. In this sense, any future updates should be understood as a refinement of its implementation in light of the experience gained through project activities, stakeholder engagement, and the progressive maturation of the Cloud.

Overall, the next phase of work will determine the practical value of the framework proposed in this deliverable. By moving from strategic definition to implementation, ECHOES will be able to test the extent to which the proposed community building model can support the emergence of a federated, collaborative, and sustainable Cultural Heritage Cloud community. In this regard, the present strategy offers the necessary framework to define as well as to guide the making and future of the Cultural Heritage Cloud community.

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3. Annexes

Annex 1: List of additional cultural heritage networks and umbrella organisations

Name of organisation	Brief description	Link to website	Link to strategy document (where available)
Architects' Council of Europe (ACE)	Representative organisation for the architectural profession at European level with 52 Member Organisations.	https://ace-cae.eu	
Artificial Intelligence for Libraries, Archives & Museums (AI4LAM)	(AI4LAM) is an international, participatory community focused on advancing the use of artificial intelligence in, for and by libraries, archives and museums.	https://ai4lam.org	
Balkan Museum Network (BMN)	Established in 2006 and facilitated by the foundation Cultural Heritage without Borders, the BMN has members in the Western Balkans region, but also in Croatia, Greece and Slovenia.	https://www.b museums.net	https://www.b museums.net/mission-vision-and-values/
Blue Shield International	Blue Shield International is a network of committees across the world to protect and safeguard cultural heritage during armed conflict and disasters.	https://theblueshield.org	https://theblueshield.org/about-us/approach-ethics-and-principles/
CLARIAH-AT	CLARIAH-AT is the consortium of Austrian universities, research and GLAM institutions that	https://clariah.at/en	https://gams.uni-graz.at/o:clariah.dha-strategie-2021

National consortium for Digital Humanities	coordinates and drives Austrian activities in the European ESFRI research infrastructures.		
ECA - European Crafts Alliance	Network with almost 40 member organisations from more than 20 European countries.	https://europeancraftsalliance.org	
EIT Culture & Creativity	EIT CC drives the future of Europe's cultural and creative industries by fostering innovation, entrepreneurship, and creative talent through their network of over 1300 partners and members.	https://eit-culture-creativity.eu	
ERRIN	European Regions Research and Innovation Network is a platform of more than 125 regional stakeholder organisations from 22 European countries.	https://errin.eu	https://errin.eu/cluster-annual-plans-2026
Europa Nostra	Covering over 40 countries, Europa Nostra is recognised as the largest and the most representative heritage network in Europe.	https://www.europanostra.org	https://issuu.com/europanostra/docs/2022-en-strategic-plan-horizon-2025
European Association for Architectural Education	Association representing architectural schools in Europe.	https://www.eaae.eu	https://www.eaae.eu/about
European Association of Archaeologists (EAA)	Association of European archaeologists with over 12,000 registered Members from 120 countries worldwide.	https://www.eaa-a.org	
European Association of History Educators (EUROCLIO)	Network of 83 Member associations representing 47 countries.	https://euroclio.eu	https://euroclio.eu/association/mission-and-vision/
European Fashion Heritage Association (EFHA)	EFHA is a network of institutions and archives promoting, preserving, and sharing Europe's fashion heritage through digital platforms and research, It	https://fashionheritage.eu	

	brings together more than 50 institutions from 15 European countries.		
European Heritage Heads Forum (EHHF)	Informal, professional and expert network for national heritage heads in the EU.	https://ehhf.eu	
European Historic Houses (EHH)	EHH represents 27 national associations of privately-owned historic houses.	https://www.ehh.eu	
European Museum Academy (EMA)	Foundation of museum experts for the advancement of knowledge in museology.	https://europeanmuseumacademy.eu	
European Music Council	Umbrella organisation dedicated to the development and promotion of music in Europe.	https://www.emc-imc.org	https://www.emc-imc.org/about/objectives-strategies
European Students' Association for Cultural Heritage (ESACH)	Youth-led interdisciplinary network of students and young professionals within cultural heritage.	https://www.esach.org	
Future for Religious Heritage (FRH)	FRH is an organisation with over 200 members from 39 countries dedicated to the safeguarding of Europe's diverse and unique religious heritage.	https://www.frh-europe.org/	https://www.frh-europe.org/about-frh/organisation
Heritage Council of Ireland	The Heritage Council is a public body whose mission is to develop a wide understanding of the vital contribution that heritage makes to social, environmental and economic well-being.	https://www.heritagecouncil.ie	https://www.heritagecouncil.ie/content/files/Strategic-Plan-2023-2028.pdf
International Council on Archives (ICA)	ICA is an international organisation which promotes the preservation and use of the world's archival heritage. It comprises around 2,000 institutional and individual members across nearly 150 countries.	https://www.ica.org	https://www.ica.org/empowering-archives-and-the-profession-2021-2024-icas-new-strategic-plan/

International Federation of Landscape Architects Europe (IFLA)	Association of 34 members representing more than 20.000 landscape architects that addresses European landscape architectural educational and professional issues.	https://iflaeuro.pe.eu	
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA)	IFLA is the leading global body representing the interests of library and information services, their users, and professionals. It represents over 1,200 members in 140+ countries.	https://www.ifla.org	https://www.ifla.org/units/strategy/
International Network for Traditional Building, Architecture and Urbanism (INTBAU)	Network on traditional building architecture which has organisations in 100 countries with 8000 members.	https://www.intbau.org	
Internationale Arbeitsgemeinschaft der Archiv-, Bibliotheks- und Graphikrestauratoren (IADA)	IADA connects professionals in the field of conservation and preservation of cultural heritage worldwide with focus on book and paper.	https://iada-home.org	https://iada-home.org/about-iada/
Interpret Europe	European Association for Heritage Interpretation with more than 800 members from more than 48 countries.	https://interpret-europe.net	https://interpret-europe.net/about/our-vision/
Museovirasto - Finnish Heritage Agency	Finnish Authority in the cultural heritage sector.	https://www.museovirasto.fi	https://www.museovirasto.fi/fi/tietoa-meista/strategia
Netwerk Digitaal Erfgoed	The Dutch Digital Heritage Network aims to develop a system of national facilities for digital heritage in The Netherlands.	https://netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl/en	https://zenodo.org/records/14760720

The Conference of European National Libraries (CENL)	CENL is a network of national libraries in Europe that collaborates to preserve cultural heritage, improve access to knowledge, and support digital innovation.	https://www.cenl.org	https://www.cenl.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/CENL_strategy2023-2027.pdf
The Future is Heritage	International network that aims to strengthen the position of young people working in the heritage field in Europe.	https://www.thefutureisheritage.com	
The International Institute for Conservation of Historic and Artistic Works (IIC)	IIC is a global organisation supporting conservation professionals through research, publications, training, and collaboration to protect cultural heritage.	https://www.iicconservation.org	https://www.iiconservation.org/sites/default/files/static/12005-iic_strategy_2030.pdf
Time Machine Organisation (TMO)	TMO is a European collaborative organisation dedicated to the development of digital “time machines” by integrating historical research, cultural heritage, and artificial intelligence technologies into a pan-European data infrastructure. TMO has over 700 members.	https://www.timemachine.eu	
Una Europa	Network of 11 European universities with cultural heritage as one of five focus areas.	https://www.una-europa.eu	https://www.una-europa.eu/about

Annex 2: First draft of the Cultural Heritage Cloud Community Charter

Principles of the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH)

The Cultural Heritage Cloud (ECCCH) is a shared digital environment that enables cultural heritage institutions, researchers, and communities across Europe to collaborate in preserving, enriching, and understanding cultural heritage in digital form. The ECCCH operates as a trusted digital commons guided by the following principles:

1. Participation and Collaboration

The ECCCH is founded on active participation and collaboration among cultural heritage institutions, researchers, professionals, and communities across Europe. It enables cross-institutional cooperation, co-creation, and communities of practice that enrich Europe's digital cultural heritage ecosystem.

Participation and collaboration in the ECCCH mean that:

1. The ECCCH fosters cross-institutional collaboration and cross-disciplinary cooperation that would not be possible in isolation, the sharing of best practices and methodologies, and opportunities for co-creation, including engagement with citizens where appropriate.
2. Users are not only consumers of services but contributors to data, knowledge, tools, and practices.
3. Mechanisms are provided to support a continuous dialogue between heritage and technical stakeholders.
4. Communities of practice are supported to emerge, grow, and sustain collaborative activities.
5. The ECCCH is governed through transparent, accountable, and representative processes that ensure equitable participation of institutions of all sizes, capacities, and regions.

2. Openness and Transparency

The ECCCH is founded on a principle of openness as a condition for collaboration, trust, and knowledge sharing across the European cultural heritage community. In the ECCCH context openness refers to openness of standards and infrastructure, openness of knowledge and reuse, openness of governance, however not ignoring IPR, sensitive heritage, or ethical limits.

Openness and Transparency in the ECCCH mean that:

1. Participation in the ECCCH is open to institutions, researchers, and communities across Europe, regardless of size or capacity.
2. The ECCCH promotes the use of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles and encourages open standards, open tools, and interoperability with existing European and international infrastructures.
3. Data, metadata, and knowledge are made as openly available as possible, while respecting intellectual property rights, ethical obligations, cultural sensitivities, and legal constraints.
4. The ECCCH is governed through transparent, accountable, and representative processes that ensure equitable participation of institutions of all sizes, capacities, and regions.
5. Policies, decisions and strategic directions are publicly shared and openly communicated.

3. Accessibility and Inclusivity

The ECCCH is committed to ensuring that all cultural heritage institutions, researchers, professionals, and communities can meaningfully access, use, and contribute to the Cultural Heritage Cloud, regardless of their size, resources, technical capacity, language, or physical abilities. Accessibility is understood as a prerequisite for equitable participation in Europe's digital cultural heritage ecosystem.

Accessibility and Inclusivity in the ECCCH mean that:

1. The ECCCH fosters equitable conditions for participation so that no community or institution is excluded from the benefits of the Cloud and diverse stakeholders are represented: cultural heritage institutions, research organisations, community groups, and technical partners from across EU Member States and Associated Countries.
2. The ECCCH lowers barriers to participation by providing user-centred and user-friendly tools, documentation, training, and support, particularly for small and medium-sized institutions.

3. Tools, services, and interfaces are designed to support a wide range of technical abilities, inclusive and compliant with recognised accessibility standards.
4. Training, documentation and support are provided to improve digital literacy among cultural heritage professionals.
5. Multilingual access and assistive technologies are supported wherever feasible.

4. Interoperability

The ECCCH is founded on interoperability as a prerequisite for collaboration, discovery, and reuse of cultural heritage resources across institutions, systems, and borders.

The ECCCH promotes shared standards, multilingual vocabularies, and open specifications so that data, tools, and services can connect, be understood, and be reused across institutions, systems, and borders, creating a coherent European digital heritage ecosystem.

Interoperability in the ECCCH means that:

1. The ECCCH is designed to connect with existing European and international infrastructures, data spaces, and platforms.
2. Data, metadata, tools, and services adhere to recognised standards and shared specifications wherever possible.
3. Multilingual vocabularies, ontologies, and controlled terminologies are promoted to enable meaningful cross-border discovery and understanding.
4. Technical and semantic interoperability are pursued to ensure that resources can be exchanged, understood, and reused across different systems and contexts.
5. Documentation and specifications are openly available to facilitate integration and reuse.

5. Sustainability and Long-term Stewardship

The ECCCH ensures the long-term stewardship of digital heritage resources and the collaborative ecosystem around them through durable infrastructure, viable governance and funding models, and practices that support preservation, reuse, and continuous evolution.

Sustainability and Long-term Stewardship in the ECCCH mean that:

1. The ECCCH is designed for long-term viability, ensuring the preservation of data, continuity of services, and sustainable governance beyond initial project phases. Infrastructure, services, and data are designed for long-term preservation, usability, and evolution.

2. The ECCCH is built on modular, scalable, and extensible architectures that evolve in response to technological advances and community needs, supporting diverse cultural heritage data types.
3. Governance, funding, and operational models are developed to ensure continuity beyond individual projects and funding cycles.
4. The ECCCH promotes environmentally responsible and resource-efficient technological choices where feasible.
5. Mechanisms for continuous evaluation, improvement and adaptation are put in place to ensure that the ECCCH remains relevant to technological developments and community needs.

For the Cloud ethical principles, see D10.1 *Founding principles of the Cloud Governance*.⁴³

⁴³ Pollé, A., et al. (2025) *ECHOES Founding principles of the Cloud Governance (D10.1)*.